

TWO PAULINE WAYS TO DESCRIBE THE ETHICS OF THE RESURRECTION LIFE

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PREFACE

Resurrection was always something that intrigued me during my years at Northeastern Seminary. This came from my interest in eschatology at Roberts Wesleyan College. I tried to use the study of the resurrection as a guide for my major term papers at seminary. I found that these papers lacked any interesting detail, and the “so what?” question was only an afterthought. I decided to continue with the theme of resurrection and focus on the “so what?” aspect. I yearned for something more than a debate over the historicity of Jesus's resurrection. That was not the question I wanted to pursue. I wanted something that will affect my life and the lives of others. So I decided to dive into ethics. It has been a difficult task to stay focused on the “how” of practicing the resurrection in Paul. It is much easier to find the pattern of resurrection living than explicit ethics. Dr. J. Richard Middleton instilled in me a passion for purposeful study of the Bible, study rooted in the original meaning and interpretation, then expanded to its effect on the cosmos.

This thesis has gone through a few drastic changes (for the better), mostly refocusing to stay within Pauline literature. The appreciation I have for Dr. Middleton’s guidance and encouragement is (hopefully) displayed on the pages below. He has pushed me to become a better person through my reading of and writing on the biblical text. My plan is to create a church discipleship program from this labor of love, something that will help the church to practically and actively live out the resurrection life in the world.

INTRODUCTION

Eschatology has an implicit ethic. However, eschatology and ethics are two disciplines that are often studied in isolation then taught with little cross-over. The study of eschatology is often exclusively associated with the end-times and events in the future. Because of partial understanding of the connectedness the church grows apathetic, which is supported by uninformed leaders who are taught by academics that do not reconcile eschatology with ethics. Many churches and schools who prepare church leaders do not see a need to prepare their people to see the fuller picture of the gospel message, which includes living a resurrection life in the present to participate with God in the reconciliation of all things. Defining the gospel message has split many churches and schools. One thing that is sorely missing from the study and living out of the gospel message is the ethics of the resurrection, and its ramification for all creation. It is increasingly difficult to study the biblical text with an interdisciplinary lens because the academy has splintered into dozens of sub-disciplines that do not talk well with each other. A beautiful dance is present in the Bible between eschatology and ethics.

Eschatology calls the reader to live an ethical life. One core element of eschatology is the resurrection, both Jesus's and all creation's. The resurrection is a highly debated topic with some questioning the historicity of Jesus's resurrection. Others question the impact it had on the inauguration of the church. However, not many question and study the impact it had on the community life of the early church and its continued ethical implications in the contemporary world. Christ's life, death, and resurrection, as eschatological events, give direction for living a resurrected lifestyle for the present. Paul's reflection on the Christ event provides a hopeful future for his audiences to actively pursue. The hopeful future is balanced by Paul's paradoxical

language of dying and rising as normal parts of life in the present. Living a life that conforms to the crucifixion requires a change in behavior as modeled by Jesus and his followers. The ultimate goal this thesis addresses is the weak, sometimes lacking, example of living a resurrected lifestyle found in the academy and its application in the church. There are many problems in addressing the complex understandings of resurrection. Resurrection life is living as though death is destroyed—the not yet—and actively seeking to dismantle death’s injustice—the already. The problem of reconciling eschatology and ethics is an unsolved problem. At least it is not fully understood in the academy and church. This thesis will attempt to reconcile resurrection and ethics. There is not much literature that tries to reconcile resurrection with ethics. How will this thesis process through the literature?

One way to narrow the study of resurrection and ethics is to focus on Paul’s use of investiture language, specifically putting on the resurrection body (1 Cor 15; 2 Cor 4–5) and new humanity, along with its practices (Eph 4; Col 3). This thesis will explore the ethics of the resurrection in two main chapters. I will be going through Paul’s language of investiture in each of the passages exegetically, starting with the context prior to each section where the investiture language is used. This thesis will explore two ways of describing resurrection ethics within the Pauline literature. The first way is described as humanity clothing itself with the resurrection body, which is described as immortal, as seen in 1 Cor 15 and 2 Cor 4–5. Mortality puts on immortality. The Corinthian correspondence provides the anthropological framework for resurrection ethics, which is fleshed out, most fully, in Eph and Col, with some groundwork laid near the end of 2 Cor 5. The second way of describing the ethics of resurrection life is found in Eph 4 and Col 3. These two chapters assume the anthropological framework laid in the

Corinthian correspondence and exhort the audience to put off the old humanity. Paul then adds specific behaviors that are associated with the old humanity, the old way of living life. Because of Christ's actions the audience is then commanded to replace the old behaviors with behaviors associated with the new humanity. These behaviors guide the community toward "true righteousness and holiness," which are "according to the image of the creator" (Eph 4:24 ; Col 3:10). The Corinthian correspondence lays the anthropological framework for the resurrection life and Eph and Col fleshes out the eschatological image of mortality putting on immortality into concrete ethical behaviors of the new humanity that replace unethical behaviors associated with the old humanity. The simple, yet powerful clothing-imagery that Paul uses to describe the ethics of the resurrection is often missed in most literature, including Jung Hoon Kim's book, *The Significance of Clothing Imagery in the Pauline Corpus*.¹ Metaphor can be a powerful tool to bring alive the ethical implications in the Pauline literature.

We will walk through 1 Cor 15 and 2 Cor 4–5, highlighting the investiture language and its impact on the world of the text. 1 Cor 15 and 2 Cor 4–5 describe one way of understanding the resurrection life. The Corinthian correspondence focuses on the anthropological impacts of the resurrection, both in the present and future of the original hearers. We will explore three sections in each 1 Cor and 2 Cor, starting with Paul's seminal work on the resurrection in 1 Cor 15.

The investiture language in Eph 4 and Col 3 is also rooted in resurrection language. Eph 4 and Col 3 takes a slightly different approach to contextualizing the investiture language. Eph links the resurrection with ethics more explicitly than the Corinthian correspondence, therefore

¹ Jung Hoon Kim, *The Significance of Clothing Imagery in the Pauline Corpus* (New York: T&T Clark International, 2004),

the behaviors attached to the new humanity are at the forefront. Eph assumes a resurrection, modeled by Jesus in Eph 4:8–10, referencing the descending and ascending of Jesus (Eph 4:10). That is the Christ whom the community has learned about (Eph 4:20). Christ is the one who was raised from the dead and gave gifts for to the new humanity (Eph 4:11–12). I focus on the practices and lifestyle of those who follow the one who descended and ascended (Eph 4:10, 17–21). Then, in Col 3, Paul explicitly links the resurrection (Col 3:1–8) with the investiture language found in the following verses (Col 3:9–10, 14). Paul builds his argument of a new way to live (through putting on and putting off behaviors) with the assumption of resurrection, saying, “so if you have been raised with Christ, seek the things that are above, where Christ is” (Col 3:1).

Eph and Col assume and builds upon the anthropological foundation Paul lays out in the Corinthian correspondence. Paul wrote Eph 4 with community unity at the center of his message and exhorts his audience to live more and more into the ways that they “learned Christ” (Eph 4:20). Paul has now moved to explain another way of resurrection life, knowing that mortality putting on immortality may be misunderstood in these communities, he provides another way to understand resurrection ethics. Paul calls his audience to put off the old humanity with its practices and replace them with behaviors that build unity within the community. The previous behaviors are contrary to the way they were taught Christ (Eph 4:17–21), instead, transformation into the renewed image of God (Eph 4:22–24) requires a new set of behaviors that builds up the community (Eph 4:25—5:2).

Paul writes the same message to the Colossian community. Paul starts Col 3 with a message to not only think of things from above, but to put to death the things that are disobedient

to God (Col 3:1–8). The behaviors that Paul points out lead to destruction, not to a fulfilling life in Christ. Paul’s message is based in his audience being raised with Christ (Col 3:1). New behaviors are to be put on. The new humanity is called to practice a lifestyle that reflects communal flourishing without seeing labels as a barrier (Col 3:9–14). The community, which is diverse, is not defined by its differences, but are to practice “compassion, kindness, humility, meekness, and patience” (Col 3:12; NRSV). This is the new set of ethical clothing humanity now wears. The second way Paul describes the resurrection life, found in Eph and Col is putting off unethical behaviors and replacing them with ethical behaviors that build up the community.

The two Pauline ways of describing the ethics of the resurrection through clothing imagery is a powerful interpretive lens for Christian living. Before we start interpreting the passages we will review the important literature. This will provide us a launching-pad for our discussion, highlighting the problems with many modern interpretations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Read dictionary entries on eschatology, resurrection, and ethics, and you might wonder why there is a need for this thesis. Let us explore a few entries in two dictionaries, one on Paul and the other on ethics. L. J. Kreitzer's "Eschatology" entry in *The Dictionary of Paul and His Letters* focuses on the Corinthian correspondence.² Kreitzer says that the power of the resurrection, empowered by the Spirit, provides a Christian ethic. However, he does not cover any of the four passages of this thesis, explicitly.³ Kreitzer's "Resurrection" entry in the same dictionary explains as Paul said in 1 Cor 15:49, that conformity to Christ's image is the goal for Christians, so the resurrection hope is to be lived into, just as followers are called to bear the image of Christ.⁴ Kreitzer also explains that Pauline ethics is closely tied to dying and rising with Christ and this participation provides an ethical lifestyle.⁵ But Kreitzer only covers 1 Cor 15. Richard Longenecker's "Resurrection" entry in *Dictionary of Scripture and Ethics* provides a good description of the pattern which this thesis builds upon.⁶ Longenecker's pattern says, Christ's resurrection, as an eschatological event, is the model of ethics that early Christians taught, which gives light to a path of a resurrected lifestyle for the present.⁷ Longenecker's pattern is sound, but does not mention an explicit ethic. Next, Thomas Finger's "Eschatology and

² L. J. Kreitzer, "Eschatology," in *Dictionary of Paul and His Letters* (ed. Gerald F. Hawthorne, Gerald F., Ralph P. Martin, and Daniel G. Reid; Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity Press, 1993), 253–269.

³ Kreitzer, "Eschatology," 264.

⁴ Kreitzer, "Resurrection," 810.

⁵ Kreitzer, "Resurrection," 810.

⁶ Richard Longenecker, "Resurrection," in *Dictionary of Scripture and Ethics* (ed. Joel B. Green, Jacqueline E. Lapsley, Rebekah Miles, and Allen Verhey; Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2011), 677–680.

⁷ Longenecker, "Resurrection," 678.

Ethics” entry brings the two topics together.⁸ Finger says, “[e]schatologically informed ethical texts envision a divinely initiated, radically different future, but one that transforms earthly life.”⁹ Finger’s pattern, however, does not cover any of the four core passages of this thesis. Finally, S. C. Mott’s “Ethics” entry lifts up Eph and Col as models of the church that “contributes to the cosmic reconciliation of all things to God.”¹⁰ Thus, the pattern for resurrection ethics is explained well by these three authors, covering several topics in these two dictionaries. These dictionaries, at first, gave me hope for plenty of sources that covered the topic of this thesis. However, what I found was that many sources ignored the connection between eschatology and ethics, failed to cover any of the four core passages of this thesis, and used simplistic, sometimes dualistic language to explain the ethics of the resurrection. Next, I will highlight relevant sources, so to provide a rationale for this thesis.

I want to look at two important works on ethics and eschatology because these two works are most often cited as the go-to sources on New Testament ethics. First, Oliver O’Donovan’s *Resurrection and Moral Order: An Outline for Evangelical Ethics* is an important work on resurrection and ethics, but in its 280 pages, O’Donovan does not cover any of the four texts that I think are critical in understanding Pauline resurrection ethics.¹¹ O’Donovan’s work on morality and resurrection is rooted in God’s act of creation of Adam and re-creation of humanity in Christ’s resurrection, however, he does not address the ethics tied to mortality putting on

⁸ Thomas Finger, “Eschatology and Ethics,” in *Dictionary of Scripture and Ethics* (ed. Joel B. Green, Jacqueline E. Lapsley, Rebekah Miles, and Allen Verhey; Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2011), 267–279.

⁹ Finger, “Eschatology and Ethics,” 267–279.

¹⁰ S.C. Mott, “Ethics,” in *Dictionary of Paul and His Letters* (ed. Gerald F. Hawthorne, Gerald F., Ralph P. Martin, and Daniel G. Reid; Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity Press, 1993), 269–275.

¹¹ Oliver O’Donovan, *Resurrection and Moral Order: An Outline for Evangelical Ethics* (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1986).

immortality and the new humanity taking off unethical behaviors and putting on new ethics for present day living. This is why I find the need to highlight these two ways of describing resurrection ethics. There is a problem when such an important work misses the simple yet powerful image of clothing to represent the transformative power of resurrection life.

The second work that has shaped Christian ethics in the last couple of decades is Richard B. Hays's *The Moral Vision of the New Testament: A Contemporary Introduction to New Testament Ethics*.¹² Pauline ethics take the foreground of his overview of New Testament Ethics. Even though, according to Hays, new creation, the cross, and a redeemed community are at the heart of Pauline ethics, the four passages this thesis covers are absent or near-absent from Hays's work. Hays does not cover any verses past 1 Cor 15:23 and 2 Cor 5:1–4 is totally absent. Eph 4:17–24 is briefly mentioned, linking to the Christian lifestyle to imitating Christ.¹³ Finally, Col 3:1–17 is missing completely as well. Hays uses powerful language to describe how the community is always exercising their “analogical imagination,” in that the community is a metaphor maker.¹⁴ What better analogy and image than resurrection ethics as clothing for the new humanity, found in Christ’s life, death, resurrection, and exaltation? O’Donovan’s and Hays's works have laid the a foundation for interpretation and practice of Christian ethics. It is my hope that this thesis presents an expanded and fresh view of Paul’s writing and description of how to live a resurrection life.

¹² Richard B. Hays, *The Moral Vision of the New Testament: A Contemporary Introduction to New Testament Ethics* (New York: HarperOne, 1996).

¹³ Hays, *The Moral Vision of the New Testament*, 64.

¹⁴ Hays, *The Moral Vision of the New Testament*, 298–299.

Indeed, many commentaries, old and new, that cover the four passages addressed in this thesis lack mention of the clothing imagery and its relation to resurrection ethics. F.F. Bruce's 1971 commentary lacks any mention of the clothing imagery.¹⁵ Murray Harris's commentary on 2 Cor mentions an "ethical" interpretation of and relationship to nakedness (2 Cor 5:3–4), but does not elaborate on his point. Ethics is not in the index as a subject either.¹⁶ Craig Keener's 2 Cor commentary clearly communicates that participation in Christ's resurrection is central to Pauline theology, yet misses the explicit connection, which this thesis will attempt to make, between resurrection and ethics, especially in 2 Cor 5:18–20.¹⁷ Anthony Thiselton's important commentary on 1 Cor does not mention resurrection ethics when discussing 1 Cor 15:49, 53–4.¹⁸

Another work that miss an opportunity to highlight the ethical implications of the resurrection includes Andrew T. Lincoln's *Paradise Now and Not Yet: Studies in the Role of the Heavenly Dimension in Paul's Thought with Special Reference to His Eschatology*.¹⁹ Lincoln covers all four passages this thesis addresses. Indeed, Lincoln affirms a non-dualistic and participatory approach when discussing the resurrection body and its impact on the present. However, he sees the example of the resurrection body as a replacement in 1 Cor 15, which is

¹⁵ F. F. Bruce, *1 and 2 Corinthians* (London: Oliphants, 1971).

¹⁶ Murray J. Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians a Commentary on the Greek Testament* (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2004), 385.

¹⁷ Craig S. Keener, *1–2 Corinthians* (Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2005).

¹⁸ Anthony C. Thiselton, *The First Epistle to the Corinthians: A Commentary on the Greek Text* (Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans, 2000).

¹⁹ Andrew T. Lincoln, *Paradise Now and Not Yet: Studies in the Role of the Heavenly Dimension in Paul's Thought with Special Reference to His Eschatology* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1981).

something this thesis argues against.²⁰ His discussion on investiture in 1 & 2 Cor focuses primarily on Paul and the parousia, not ethics. Lincoln's later chapters on Eph and Col do not mention the investiture language present in Eph 4 and Col 3.

Both Terrance Callan's and Constantine Campbell's works on Pauline theology deal with participatory ways of understanding Christ's death and resurrection.²¹ However, Callan limits his discussion of ethics to slavery and marital relationship, missing any connection back to the investiture he covered. Campbell also misses an opportunity to link clothing imagery (especially the image in 1 Cor 15:49, which is about bearing the image of Christ) to union with Christ, which is the title of his work after all.

Jung Hoon Kim's detailed work has plenty of material that adds to the discussion on resurrection, but lacks a holistic picture of eschatology and ethics. On several occasions, Kim writes with simplistic and clearly dualistic claims when discussing Paul's eschatology in the four core passages this thesis covers. The transformation that Paul wrote about in 1 Cor 15 is not, as Kim says, "the transformation of the immortal soul's transformation into its heavenly mode."²² There are other points where Kim criticizes gnostic and other dualistic approaches,²³ yet he falls into the same dualistic patterns when explaining the complicated nature of the resurrection and

²⁰ Lincoln, *Paradise Now and Not Yet*, 50. A discussion of replacement versus transformation and fulfillment will come later in this thesis.

²¹ Terrance Callan, *Dying and Rising with Christ: The Theology of Paul the Apostle* (New York: Paulist Press, 2006). Constantine Campbell, *Paul and Union with Christ: An Exegetical and Theological Study* (Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 2012).

²² Jung Hoon Kim, *The Significance of Clothing Imagery in the Pauline Corpus* (New York: T&T Clark International, 2004), 204.

²³ Kim, *The Significance of Clothing Imagery*, 194.

eschatology.²⁴ Because Kim's work is so focused on the imagery, I wished there would be more attention given to ethics, since imagery is a great way to help people understand a change in behavior. This is exactly what I argue Paul is doing when he used investiture language in the four core passages covered in this thesis.

Now, we take a turn toward literature that begins to address the idea of resurrection ethics, without explicitly addressing the four core passages of this thesis. Brian V. Johnstone chapter in *The Resurrection: An Interdisciplinary Symposium on the Resurrection of Jesus* gives a powerful foundation of resurrection ethics, however he interacts very little or not at all with the four core passage this thesis addresses.²⁵ The clothing imagery is simple and powerful when trying to understand resurrection ethics. Douglas J. Moo's "Creation and New Creation" essay argues that there is an integral connection between new creation and resurrection life, which is something this thesis begins to unpack.²⁶ Moo summarizes the purpose of resurrection living is to bring others from death to life, in Christ.²⁷ Paul is saying something very similar to what Moo is saying, so it is hard to criticize Moo's work, even though he does not address the four core passages of this thesis. Christopher Bryan's *The Resurrection of the Messiah* deals with present day transformation when talking about resurrection.²⁸ However, the four core passages of this thesis are absent.

²⁴ Kim, *The Significance of Clothing Imagery*, 213, where Kim argues 2 Cor 5:8 describes the soul leaving the body.

²⁵ Brian V. Johnstone, "Transformation Ethics: The Moral Implications of the Resurrection" in *The Resurrection: An Interdisciplinary Symposium on the Resurrection of Jesus* (ed. Stephen Thane Davis; Oxford, NY: Oxford University Press, 1998).

²⁶ Douglas J. Moo, "Creation and New Creation," *Bulletin For Biblical Research* 20/1 (2010): 39–60.

²⁷ Moo, "Creation and New Creation," 58.

²⁸ Christopher Bryan, *The Resurrection of the Messiah* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2011).

Now, let us turn to the most important works that deal with 1 and 2 Cor, the first two core passages of this thesis. James P. Ware’s article in the *Journal of Biblical Literature* closely covers the core verses in 1 Cor 15 that deal with resurrection ethics.²⁹ Ware discusses the transformation of mortality into immortality through an “eschatological restoration to life.”³⁰ Ware also affirms a materiality and consistency between the present mortal body that clothes itself with immortality.³¹ John G. Lewis covers mostly the passage in 1 Cor 15.³² When discussing 1 Cor 15:49, Lewis argues that the individual and in turn the community is transformed through behavioral changes to become more Christ-like.³³ Lewis says, “1 Cor 15:58 illuminates the nature of the victory that God is giving through the Lord Jesus Christ to believers who experience new life by conforming their actions to Christ’s cruciform pattern.”³⁴ Michael Gorman has written extensively on the idea of “cruciformity,” which this thesis will explore in both chapters.³⁵ Gorman says the goal of cruciformity that is rooted in Paul’s call to bear the image of Christ in 1 Cor 15:49 starts “through an ongoing experience of sharing in Christ’s status as a slave or servant of God and

²⁹ James P. Ware, “Paul’s Understanding of the Resurrection in 1 Corinthians 15:36–54,” *Journal of Biblical Literature* 133/4 (2014): 809–835.

³⁰ Ware, “Paul’s Understanding of the Resurrection,” 817.

³¹ Ware, “Paul’s Understanding of the Resurrection,” 825.

³² John G. Lewis, *Looking for Life: The Role of "Theo-Ethical Reasoning" in Paul's Religion* (London: T&T Clark International, 2005).

³³ Lewis, *Looking for Life*, 137.

³⁴ Lewis, *Looking for Life*, 140.

³⁵ Michael J. Gorman, *Cruciformity: Paul's Narrative Spirituality of the Cross* (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2001) and Michael J. Gorman, *Inhabiting the Cruciform God: Kenosis, Justification, and Theosis in Paul's Narrative Soteriology* (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2009).

others, one characterized by non-retaliatory, other-centered love."³⁶ It is "a participation in Christ's cross."³⁷ Thus, the paradox of cruciformity: death in order to give life.³⁸

Paul J. Brown writes explicitly on the topic of ethics of the resurrection in his book, *Bodily Resurrection and Ethics in 1 Cor 15: Connecting Faith and Morality in the Context of Greco-Roman Mythology*.³⁹ His work, along with Jane Fejfer's *Roman Portraits in Context*,⁴⁰ provides an understanding of image-representation in 1 Cor 15:49. Brown then links the ethical urging in 1 Cor 15:49 to 1 Cor 15:58.⁴¹ Gordon D. Fee writes in his commentary on 1 Cor that 1 Cor 15:49, "[t]he urgency is that they truly [bear the likeness of Christ] now as they await the consummation when they shall do so fully."⁴²

Next, let us turn to works that cover the second two, core passages of this thesis, Eph 4 and Col 3. Walter G. Hansen writes that transformation of a person's character happens when they participate, as "new moral agents" in God's redemptive activity in the world.⁴³ This

³⁶ Gorman, *Inhabiting the Cruciform God*, 113.

³⁷ Gorman, *Inhabiting the Cruciform God*, 113.

³⁸ This paradox will be examined further later in the thesis.

³⁹ Paul J. Brown, *Bodily Resurrection and Ethics in 1 Cor 15: Connecting Faith and Morality in the Context of Greco-Roman Mythology* (Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2014).

⁴⁰ Jane Fejfer, *Roman Portraits in Context* (Berlin: de Gruyter, 2008).

⁴¹ Brown, *Bodily Resurrection and Ethics in 1 Cor 15*, 231.

⁴² Gordon D. Fee, *The First Epistle to the Corinthians* (Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans, 1987), 795.

⁴³ G. Walter Hansen, "Resurrection and the Christian Life in Paul's Letters," in *Life in the Face of Death: The Resurrection Message of the New Testament* (ed. Richard N. Longenecker; Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1998), 211.

transformation is explained in Col 3 and Eph 4 through the image of putting off unethical behaviors and putting on ethical behaviors.⁴⁴

In his most recent book, *A New Heaven and a New Earth: Reclaiming Biblical Eschatology*, J. Richard Middleton affirms “the continuity of identity between the seed (mortal body) and the plant (resurrection body).”⁴⁵ This is the theme of the second chapter, mortality putting on immortality. Middleton also affirms a changed lifestyle because of the investiture of the new humanity in Eph 4 and Col 3.⁴⁶ This is the theme of the third chapter, taking off the unethical behaviors and putting on ethical behaviors in their place. Middleton finishes his chapter, “Resurrection and the Restoration of Rule” by saying, “[i]ndeed, hope of resurrection can be a significant spur to action in the present as the church seeks to manifest God’s kingdom in daily life.”⁴⁷ My hope, in writing this thesis, is to bring two ways Paul describes the ethics of the resurrection life, which leads to more healthy and holistic practice of Christian ethics in the church and academy that benefits the world.

⁴⁴ Hansen, “Resurrection and the Christian Life in Paul’s Letters,” 212.

⁴⁵ J. Richard Middleton, *A New Heaven and a New Earth: Reclaiming Biblical Eschatology* (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2014), 202.

⁴⁶ Middleton, *A New Heaven and a New Earth*, 203.

⁴⁷ Middleton, *A New Heaven and a New Earth*, 154.

CHAPTER 1

ANTHROPOLOGY AND ETHICS: RESURRECTION LIFE IN 1 AND 2 CORINTHIANS

Eschatology has an implicit ethic, yet the the discussion and practice of ethics tied to eschatology is uncommon in the scholarly literature and church teachings. Paul strongly ties together ethics with eschatology. To get a better understanding of Pauline eschatological ethics, specifically resurrection ethics, we will first explore two passages from the Pauline literature, in which the investiture language in the Corinthian correspondence is one way of describing resurrection ethics.

Because the topic of eschatology and ethics is so broad, we will first focus on investiture language of bearing or wearing (φορέω) and putting on or clothing (ἐνδύω) found in 1 Cor 15:49 and 53–54. This sets up the foundation for similar language of carrying around (περιφέρω) and being further clothed (ἐπενδύομαι) in 2 Cor 4:10 and 5:2–4. These two passages describe one way of the resurrection life. Paul called the Corinthian community to live counter-cultural lives, contrary to the way of the Roman Empire, lives that bear the image (1 Cor 15:49) and death (2 Cor 4:10) of Jesus and put on the resurrection body (1 Cor 15:53–54; 2 Cor 5:2–4), which in turn empowers the message of reconciliation to be lived out (2 Cor 5:18–21).

Both chapters finish with an ethical foundation to live by. 1 Cor 15 finishes with an exhortation to be “steadfast, immovable, as if super-abounding in the work of the Lord always” (1 Cor 15:58).⁴⁸ This verse ends Paul’s conversation on the resurrection, specifically believer’s resurrection, with an ethical urging. Later, Paul finishes his resurrection section in 2 Cor 4–5 with a message to live a life that works toward reconciliation of all things (2 Cor 5:18–21). My

⁴⁸ All translations in Chapter 1 are my own, unless otherwise noted.

analysis of the the Corinthian correspondence makes the case that Paul's use of investiture, grounded in the hope of a future resurrection, generates an alternative praxis for Christian living in the image of the risen Christ for present day life; one way of describing the resurrection life.

I. Investiture Language in 1 Corinthians 15

1 Cor 15 covers a lot of ground related to resurrection and eschatology. After affirming Christ's resurrection as the climax of the story Paul received and passed on (15:1–11) he addresses objections to the resurrection of those who follow Christ (15:12 and 35), in the process expounding on the relationship of Christ's resurrection to the expected resurrection of believers (15:12–34) and the nature of the resurrection body (12:35–57). Then, in conclusion, Paul succinctly draws out the ethical consequences of this future hope for life in the present (15:58).

Where Paul lays out the nature of the resurrection body in 1 Cor 15, he uses language of investiture and clothing with two words, φορέω (to wear/bear) and ἐνδύω (to put on/clothe). In the first half of this chapter, we will walk through the specific sections of 1 Cor 15 where investiture language occurs (15:49, 53–54). These verses are two ethical anchors of the passage and the foundation for exploring Paul's use of similar words in 2 Cor 4–5, which we will explore later on in this chapter.

First, we will examine the context of the first image of investiture language appears (15:48–49), in verses 42–46. These two sets of verses (42–46 and 48–49) constitute the context of the second image of investiture language in verses 53–54, which is slightly more complex to understand. We will explore specific language Paul uses to compare the current state of things and the state that believers are called to live into. We will start by exploring Paul's use of sowing a ψυξτικός (soulish) and raising a πνευματικός (spiritual) body (1 Cor 15:42–46). Then we will

look at φορέω (to bear/wear) in verse 49, and how bearing the image of the first and last Adam (1 Cor 15:45–49) relates to putting on (ἐνδύω) in verses 53–54. Next, we will take a closer look at the two verses where ἐνδύω is used (1 Cor 15:53–54). In that section we will look at Paul’s use of an Old Testament passage.

Paul borrows language and themes from an Old Testament text in 53–54. Examining Paul’s use of imagery from Isa 25 in 1 Cor 15:53–54 will shed some light on how a contemporary ethic can be reached. The larger-than-life image of God swallowing the covering of death in Isa 25 grounds Paul’s nuanced context for the practical clothing imagery that sets his argument for resurrection living. We will finish the study of 1 Cor 15 with a look at possible misunderstandings the Corinthian community had with Paul’s clothing imagery. A misunderstanding or unwillingness to bear the resurrection life could be one reason why Paul reiterates and clarifies the ethic tied to the resurrection in his second letter to the Corinthian community. Paul makes sure his audience knows that there are ethics intimately connected to the resurrection; ethics that are lived daily on this earth, not somewhere in a distant disembodied state.

A. Humanity’s Lively Disobedience is Sown but Jesus’s Life-Giving Spirit Raises (1 Corinthians 15:42–46)

⁴²And thus the resurrection of the dead: it is sown in corruption, it is raised up incorruptible; ⁴³it is sown in disgrace, it is raised up in glory; it is sown in weakness, it is raised up in power. ⁴⁴It is sown a soulish body, it is raised up a spiritual body. If there is a soulish body, then there is spiritual body. ⁴⁵And thus it is written, the first human, Adam, was made into a soul, in order to live; the last Adam into spirit, in order to make alive.

⁴⁶But it is not the spiritual first, rather the soulish, then the spiritual. (1 Cor 15:42–46)

Paul describes the progressive stages of the resurrection body. He describes it as a seed (1 Cor 15:37) sown corruptible, disgraced, weak, soulish, then raised incorruptible, glorified,

powerful, and spiritual (1 Cor 15:42–44). Humanity was once full of life, but because of disobedience the image is partially corrupted, disgraced, weak, and remains soulish, or ordinary.

Two words often misused in the church today are natural/physical (ψυχικός) and spiritual (πνευματικός). Surprisingly, they go unexplained in the text, assuming the Corinthian community knew these terms well. Also, Paul’s use of ψυχικός (soulish), found only in 1 Cor 2 and 15, may be a leading factor in mistranslations of the word throughout church history. On the other hand, Paul used πνευματικός (spiritual) fifteen times in 1 Cor, more than his other letters combined. The two words are misunderstood today and translated different ways in modern translations. The ASV, ESV, KJV, NASB, NET, NIV 2011, NKJV, WEB all translated ψυχικός as “natural.” The CEB and NRSV translate it as “physical,” which may lead to a deeper false dichotomy between physical and spiritual.

N. T. Wright translates ψυχικός as “ordinary nature.”⁴⁹ While Wright’s translation merely adds “ordinary” to the idea of nature or natural, it clarifies Paul’s main point quite well. Ordinary is the status quo; it is inherited throughout the generations, starting with the first Adam (1 Cor 15:45). Then, something radically different happens. A new humanity is born in Jesus. The former, ordinary nature of humanity, found in the first Adam, is transformed in the last Adam. This way of life is dramatically contrasted to the last Adam, who is Jesus. However, the first Adam is not forgotten, but instead the core elements of the original intent are recovered by the last Adam. A new ordinary becomes possible through the last Adam. Paul further contrasts the first Adam and his implied mortality to the last Adam and the resurrection that occurs. The

⁴⁹ N. T. Wright, *The Kingdom New Testament: A Contemporary Translation* (New York: HarperCollins, 2011), 362.

ordinary nature of humanity, found in the first Adam, was wrapped in an image to live into something greater, the last Adam.

While this life is surrounded by death, it does not necessarily mean that death is evil, but instead a part of the process, “thus the resurrection of the dead” (1 Cor 15:42a). Paul provides hope to be lived into; hope that is grounded in reality. The souliness of humanity is not the end, but a beginning. It is not something to forget, but to be developed and nurtured into something new, the last Adam.

The contrasting nature of the resurrection (1 Cor 15:42–44) is then elaborated upon in verse 45 where Paul adapts Genesis 2:7, which reads, “and the man became a living soul” (my translation from the LXX). Paul adds the words *πρῶτος* (first) and *Ἀδάμ* (Adam). This sets up the point of these verses: the first Adam, who represents a now inherently disobedient humanity was intended for great things. The first Adam was created as a soul in order to live into the image of God. Because of humanity’s misuse of power, a creative power that is inherent in the image of God, the last Adam, God incarnate, came to earth as an embodied human, in order to make others alive and to give direction in becoming truly human.⁵⁰

I have interpreted the two phrases in verse 45, “ἐγένετο ὁ πρῶτος ἄνθρωπος Ἀδάμ εἰς ψυχὴν ζῶσαν and ὁ ἔσχατος Ἀδάμ εἰς πνεῦμα ζωοποιῶν” as follows: “the first human, Adam was made into a soul, in order to live and the last Adam into a spirit, in order to make alive” (1 Cor 15:45). Thus, Paul argues that ζῶσαν (the present active participle of ζάω, ‘to live’) and ζωοποιῶν (a participle of ζωοποιέω, ‘to make live’) are ways of life that contrast purpose; the first Adam’s life, characterized by mortality, versus the last Adam’s life-giving purpose and

⁵⁰ For more on this comparison, see Brown, *Bodily Resurrection and Ethics*, 208–219.

eventual resurrection. The life of the first Adam is marked by life and death while the last Adam is marked by a purpose to make others alive (ζωοποιῶν) through his life, death, resurrection, and ascension to the right hand of God, each particular ways of representing true humanity.

The comparison of ordinary living and new-life-giving strengthens Paul's later use of investiture language he calls his audience to bear/wear (φορέω) in verse 49. Humanity was first created to live into the image of God, but through disobedience, humanity became corrupt. Because of this corruption, Jesus came to give life to others (1 Cor 15:42–45), in order that the tarnished image of humanity be recovered. Living into the recovered image of the last Adam is the same lifestyle, to give life for others, that Paul urges his audience to bear in 1 Cor 15:49. The call (15:49) is also built on what Paul says in 15:21–23 about Adam bringing death, and Christ bringing resurrection (1 Cor 15:21). All will be made alive in Christ (15:22), because of Christ's first fruit example (15:23). Paul's use of sowing and raising is reminiscent of birth, death, and new birth. "What you sow does not come to life unless it dies. And as for what you sow, you do not sow the body that is to be, but a bare seed, perhaps of wheat or of some other grain" (1 Cor 15:36–37; NRSV). Our incorruptible, glorified, and powerful bodies come only through death to the ordinary way of perpetuating death for others. Life is found in Christ's life-giving spirit, modeled by how Christ lived as a first fruits for others. Only then can humanity be a life-giving people, bearing the image of Christ and participating in God's redemption of all things, assuming all flesh, including humans, animals, birds, and fish, as well as the heavenly and earthly bodies (15:39–40) will be redeemed too (15:42).⁵¹

⁵¹ After explaining the differences between different flesh and bodies, Paul moves to say, "thus the resurrection of the dead" (1 Cor 15:42), making the link that the same will happen with all flesh and bodies.

B. *Bearing the Renewed and Resurrected Image of Christ (1 Corinthians 15:48–49)*

⁴⁸As was the one of dust, so are those of the dust, and as was the one of heaven, so are those of heaven. ⁴⁹And just as we have borne the image of the dusty one, let us also bear the image of the heavenly one. (1 Cor 15:48–49)

Paul now compares heaven with earth with a purpose to urge a current, combined living experience—live a heavenly life on earth. Paul calls his audience to acknowledge their history in the man of dust, the first Adam, but to put on another image, the heavenly one, Jesus (1 Cor 15:48–49). The first image is not to be disregarded. “Let us also bear...” gives a sense of having both present. The earthy nature of the first Adam is not to be thrown away. Christ lived a lifestyle that reflected the true intention for humanity. Paul contrasts these ways of living by telling the story of humanity throughout the ages, from the first Adam to Christ. Paul urged his audience to understand the mortality innate in humanity, but to embrace the fullness of humanity, found in Christ.

I have used the manuscripts where φορέσωμεν (let us bear/wear) appears. There is a wide range of early texts that support the subjunctive.⁵² The debate goes back to early church history. Tertullian argues the indicative against Marcion’s subjunctive.⁵³ Chrysostom, Cyprian, and Basil prefer the subjunctive.⁵⁴ I argue for the aorist subjunctive and will exegete the text below. There are only two major English translations that use the manuscripts that have φορέω as an aorist subjunctive (φορέσωμεν) instead of a future indicative (φορέσομεν). The New English

⁵² Ἰ⁴⁶ ⲛ A C D F G Ψ 075 0243 33 1739 Ἰ latt bo.

⁵³ Tertullian, *Against Marcion*, 5:10.

⁵⁴ Chrysostom, *1 Cor. Hom.*, 42:2; Cyprian, *Against the Jews*, 10.

⁵⁵ For an in depth discussion on the history of interpretation of verse 49, see Thiselton, *The First Epistle to the Corinthians*, 1288–1289.

Translation says, “And just as we have borne the image of the man of dust, let us also bear the image of the man of heaven” (1 Cor 15:49; NET). The aorist subjunctive, used in the NET, is a more difficult reading, whereas the more uncommonly found future indicative was most likely a later scribal edit. While the aorist subjunctive is a more difficult reading (it doesn’t fit context of surrounding indicatives), it is used more often in the New Testament than the future indicative.⁵⁶

The Message paraphrase reads in similar fashion, saying, “In the same way that we’ve worked from our earthy origins, let’s embrace our heavenly end” (1 Cor 15:49; MSG). While this is a poor, other-worldly paraphrase of the latter part of verse 49, The Message still uses the sense from the hortatory subjunctive, let us embrace. It is more likely that it was originally an aorist subjunctive (which has more textual support) then later edited to, as Gordon Fee said, “a clearly understandable future.”⁵⁷ Paul says no to the ideas of an existence void of both physicality and ethics. The Corinthians are still in the likeness of the first Adam, but because of Christ’s resurrection, they are called to live into the likeness of Christ. Because of the greater text support for an original φορέσωμεν, paired with its more difficult reading, I am using the aorist subjunctive, φορέσωμεν, “let us bear” (1 Cor 15:49). Let us put on the image of Christ! This hortatory reading lends to the eschatological tension found in Paul’s argument, here and in Col 3:10, which we will explore in the next chapter.

Paul’s call to bear the image of Christ (1 Cor 15:49), helps clear up the mysterious meaning of verse 50; “flesh and blood is not able to inherit the kingdom of God, neither the corruptible inherit the incorruptible” (1 Cor 15:50). “Flesh and blood” is another way of saying

⁵⁶ NET 1 Cor 15: 49, note 27.

⁵⁷ Fee, *The First Epistle to the Corinthians*, 795

“ordinary nature” (1 Cor 15:44; *Kingdom New Testament*) or “those of the dust” (1 Cor 15:49). Through continual disobedience, humanity’s ordinary nature has become corrupt, disgraceful, and weak (1 Cor 15:42–43). The ordinary has transformed into a twisted sense of God’s intention. Paul sees a way through the disobedience, corruption, disgrace, and weakness, which is an intentional lifestyle change. Paul understands resurrection ethics in a participatory way that calls others to bear the image of Christ (1 Cor 15:49) in a radically transformative way. Paul Brown made the point that the Corinthians would have made the connection between εἰκών and ethics.⁵⁸ Brown points out that the image representation, through honorific statues, “served to set benefactors up as examples to be followed.”⁵⁹ Both the first and last Adam are examples to follow. One was given life, but because of disobedience life did not flourish as God intended. The image of the last Adam is another example to follow. What did the Corinthians think when they heard Paul’s language of images?

The Roman statues, as Jane Fejfer said, “provided *exempla* for future generations of the kind of generosity and good behaviour that would promote the common good and the fame of the city.”⁶⁰ Paul used image-representation to root his argument in creation language and the surrounding worldviews from Genesis then paired it with the Roman idea of honor associated with benefactors.⁶¹ Interpreting Paul’s message and call to the Corinthian community, in light of this Roman lens, gives greater clarity on the close tie of ethics and resurrection in 1 Cor 15.

⁵⁸ Brown, *Bodily Resurrection and Ethics*, 218–219.

⁵⁹ Brown, *Bodily Resurrection and Ethics*, 218.

⁶⁰ Jane Fejfer, *Roman Portraits in Context* (Berlin: de Gruyter, 2008), 20.

⁶¹ For more on this, see Fejfer, *Roman Portraits in Context*.

There is a moral imperative intimately involved in choosing between the first and last Adam. Is the community going to seek the ordinary, yet tarnished image of the first Adam, or are they going to seek a greater and more whole image of Christ, the heavenly one. As we will explore in the second half of the chapter, the new ordinary that is found in the heavenly is counter-cultural in many ways, possibly leading to a misunderstanding and rejection of following the example of Christ in the Corinthian community.

The transformation of the first and last Adam (1 Cor 15:45–48) with Paul’s explicit clothing imagery (1 Cor 15:53–54), connected by the exhortation in verse 49, “let us bear” (φορέσωμεν), makes this passage crucial in understanding Christian ethics. Exploring this connection of Paul’s clothing imagery—putting on incorruption and immortality (15:53–4) to bearing the image of the first and last Adam (15:45–9)—will leave us with a better understanding of Paul’s overall use and message and ethic of the investiture language. To do this, we will explore the similarities between φορέω (to bear/wear), and ἐνδύω (to put on).

The active participation in bearing Jesus's image (1 Cor 15:49) is closely linked to putting on the resurrection body as clothing (1 Cor 15:53–54). The word φορέω (1 Cor 15:49) is synonymous with the word ἐνδύω, and its various forms, in 1 Cor 15:53–54 (cf. 2 Cor 5:1–5; Eph 4:24; Col 3:9–11, 12). The metaphor of bearing “the image of the heavenly one” (1 Cor 15:49) “is a metaphor for putting on clothing. Cf. the same metaphor with the verb ἐνδύω in vv. 53–54 and 2 Cor. 5:1–4.”⁶² Understanding the common strand between the two words, Paul urges his audience to see the similarity of putting on incorruptibility and immortality and bearing the image of Jesus. Φορέω occurs a few times in the New Testament.⁶³ When φορέω is used outside

⁶² Fee, *The First Epistle to the Corinthians*, 794, n. 34.

⁶³ Matt 11:8; John 19:5; Rom 13:4; 1 Cor 15:49; and Jas 2:3.

the New Testament, it has a sense of continually carrying.⁶⁴ Even though it is an aorist active subjunctive, it seems likely Paul wanted his audience to put the image on and keep it on, rather than put it on once and not think about it again. There is a sense of transformation involved.

Bearing the image of the first and last Adam is ingrained in the lives of all humanity

Pairing the aorist subjunctive (hortatory reading) with the prevalent meaning of continuous bearing elsewhere, Paul's call is intensified in verse 49. Paul calls the Corinthians to make an ethical connection to the image of the heavenly one that is Christ. Paul calls them to continually bear the image of Christ, which requires a radical change in lifestyle. The use of φορέω in verse 49 as continually wearing/bearing the image of Jesus is reiterated in Paul's use of ἐνδύω in verses 53–54. As Andrew Lincoln describes in his book, *Paradise Now and Not Yet*, Paul's comparison of the first and last Adam is not simply about a restoration of an image lost in the first Adam, but instead involves a new quality of life.⁶⁵ Paul's use of creation language seems to be making the point that God did something unique in the first Adam and is doing something again in the last Adam. However, the last Adam is fulfilling the original purpose of the first Adam. This new quality of life is the recovery of the *imago dei*; Christ modelling what it means to be truly human. Parts of the seed remain and something beautiful and new comes from the seed. It is not something entirely new. Even though Christ has already modelled this new way of life, breaking open like a beautiful flower from a seed, the dirt and mud still remain with us. Paul's audience is getting a full picture of what the goal is and how to live before the goal is finally accomplished.

⁶⁴ K. Weiss, "φορέω," in *Theological Dictionary of the New Testament*, trans. Geoffrey W. Bromiley (ed. Gerhard Friedrich; Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1974), 84.

⁶⁵ For more, see Lincoln, *Paradise Now and Not Yet*, 50–4.

The tension of the ‘already’ and ‘not yet’ appears in verses 48–49 and 53–54. This tension, however, is part of participatory living. This is the same tension Paul is speaking directly to in the Corinthian community. The Corinthians, Fee says, “believed that they had already assumed the heavenly existence that was to be, an existence in the Spirit that discounted earthly existence both in its physical and in its behavioral expressions.”⁶⁶ This kind of over-realized eschatology falls in suit with Anthony Thiselton’s 1978 article, “Realized Eschatology at Corinth” in *New Testament Studies*. Fleshing out the classical view of the Corinthian community having an over-realized eschatology and recent literature arguing against the classical view is not important to my argument.⁶⁷ Whether the Corinthian community actually believed the resurrection had fully taken place or not, Paul’s linking of bearing the image of Christ and putting on the resurrection body makes the case that the Corinthian community needed encouragement to actively participate in Christ’s life. Tension is part of fully engaging the image of Jesus, who is the new humanity. The tension continues in the urgency and necessity of putting on the resurrection body in the present with the future consummation of death’s defeat 1 Cor 15:54–55. The eschatological ethic that is ingrained in investiture language of bearing the image of Christ and putting on the resurrection body was a reality for the Corinthians and continues to be for the contemporary church today. Humans are made up of earthly creatures, called to reflect the image of Christ’s resurrection, which is a heavenly task. Lincoln said, “they are heavenly not

⁶⁶ Gordon D. Fee, *The First Epistle to the Corinthians*, 795.

⁶⁷ For more on the idea of realized eschatology, see Anthony C. Thiselton, “Realized Eschatology at Corinth,” in *New Testament Studies* 24/4 (1978) and David M. Beary, “Over-realized Eschatology and the Recipients of Paul’s First Epistle to the Corinthians” (Ph.D. Diss., Dallas Theological Seminary, 2006).

because they came from heaven or are going to heaven, but because they are ‘in Christ’ (cf. 1 Cor 15:22) and share his resurrection life.”⁶⁸

This kind of earthy and participatory line of thinking challenges the predominant philosophy of the modern era, which embraces the immortality of the soul instead of the resurrection of the body.⁶⁹ Jung Hoon Kim links the “culmination of resurrection immortality” to “the immortal soul’s transformation into its heavenly mode.”⁷⁰ This helps to show the power behind the ancient, but not biblical, philosophy of the immortality of the soul. The philosophy is taught and practiced by many in the modern era. Can someone be resurrected if they are already immortal? No, someone must fully die before they are resurrected. The pervasiveness of the immortality of the soul is seen across the contemporary church and academy.

However, sharing in Jesus's resurrection life is rooted in bearing that renewed image daily. John G. Lewis links the language of bearing the image of Jesus with ethics by saying there is a “new, divinely approved social norm of self-giving love for others manifest in the death of Jesus Christ.”⁷¹ A new social norm was made possible because Jesus challenged the false-hope of a violent salvation by sacrificing himself to bring healing. Bearing the renewed image of Jesus is brought to a climax with Paul’s use of eschatological imagery, being clothed with incorruptibility and immortality, and the defeat of death (1 Cor 15:53–54). The eschatologically

⁶⁸ Lincoln, *Paradise Now and Not Yet*, 50.

⁶⁹ See Oscar Cullmann, *The Immortality of the Soul or the Resurrection of the Dead?: The Witness of the New Testament* (New York: Macmillan, 1958).

⁷⁰ Kim, *The Significance of Clothing Imagery*, 204.

⁷¹ Lewis, *Looking for Life*, 139.

transformative practice putting on incorruptibility and immortality is wrapped up in ordinary imagery, the image of clothing.

C. The Necessary Transformational Clothing of Resurrection (1 Corinthians 15:53–54)

⁵³For it is necessary that this corrupt [body] put on incorruptibility and this mortal [body] put on immortality. ⁵⁴But whenever this corrupt body puts on incorruptibility and this mortal body puts on immortality, then the word that was written will be fulfilled: “Death has been devoured in victory. (1 Cor 15:53–54)

Verse 53 begins with the use of δεῖ (it is necessary). Kim suggests δεῖ answers the prior statement from verse 50, “flesh and blood is not able to inherit the kingdom of God, neither the corruptible inherit the incorruptible” (1 Cor 15:50).⁷² Herein lies the continued tension of transformation. Our nature of existence in the present is not able to inherit the kingdom of God, at least not fully, until a radical change occurs. Humanity is called to bear the image of Jesus (1 Cor 15:49) and put on incorruptibility and immortality (1 Cor 15:53–54). Bearing the image of Jesus is a radical choice to make and the eventual transformation of the body is super-radical. The radical transformation develops in daily decisions; to bear the life-giving image of Jesus, who represents the new humanity (1 Cor 15:45). This transformation, developed in daily decisions, is the necessary component for resurrection ethics.

Verse 53 names the requirement of transformation and answers verse 50, when it says, “it is necessary that this corrupt body put on incorruptibility and this mortal body put on immortality.” One must “put on” certain things before transformation can take place. Verse 50 states that the corruptible “is not able” to inherit the incorruptible, yet verse 53 says “it is necessary.” The change is not possible only, it is necessary. It is only possible by daily decisions to put on the new clothing of Christ. Paul acknowledges the present life (1 Cor 15:50) and the

⁷² Kim, *The Significance of Clothing Imagery*, 204.

desired goal (1 Cor 15:53). Paul urges believers to live a different life, a life that mirrors the image of the heavenly one (1 Cor 15:49). The relationship between bearing the renewed image of Christ (15:49) and putting on a new kind of clothing (15:53–54) is complex, to say the least.

However, taking a look at Paul’s use of an Old Testament passage might help. Paul uses material from Isa 25 and applies similar themes to his context. Isa’s context of the relationship of clothing and the defeat of death is important to understand the lens Paul uses to write about clothing and its relation to resurrection. The Old Testament passage Paul references in 1 Cor 15:54b is not only important to understand life and death but also Paul’s use of a covering and clothing. In verse 54b, Paul uses a Greek text different from the Greek Old Testament or Masoretic Text we have today. The LXX reading of Isa 25:7–8, translated by Moisés Silva, reads: “Deliver all these things to the nations on this mountain, for this counsel is against all the nations. Death, having prevailed, swallowed them up, and God has again taken away every tear from every face.”⁷³ The MT says, “he [God] will swallow up death forever.” There is, however, agreement between Paul, Aquila, and both of Theodotion’s readings of Isa 25:8. Paul, Aquila, and Theodotion’s readings have *death* being swallowed or drowned *in victory*.

The MT reading of Isa 25:7–8 implies the covering or veil cast over the nations is death itself. It is interesting to note the different use of covering in the Isa 25 (MT) passage and Paul’s letters. Walter Harrelson says “the covering referred to in [Isa 25:7; MT] is a negative reality, one that God must remove in order that the eschatological feast may proceed.”⁷⁴ Removal of certain

⁷³ Moisés Silva, “Esaias,” in *A New English Translation of the Septuagint: And the Other Greek Translations Traditionally Included Under That Title* (ed. Albert Pietersma and Benjamin G. Wright; New York: Oxford University Press, 2007), 842.

⁷⁴ Walter Harrelson, “Death and Victory in 1 Corinthians 15:51–57: The Transformation of a Prophetic Theme,” in *Faith and History: Essays in Honor of Paul W. Meyer* (ed. John T. Carroll, Charles H. Cosgrove, and E. Elizabeth Johnson; Atlanta: Scholars Press, 1990), 152.

items is more in line with Eph 4:22–24, which I will address in the next chapter. However, here in 1 Cor 15:53–56 Paul speaks of clothing as something positive and also speaks of lives transformed not just for a feast, as found in Isa 25, but a new reality.

The image of the first Adam, corruptible and mortal, are coverings not taken away or removed as the covering is in Isa; instead they are recovered. Just as humanity's image was tarnished, found in the image of Adam, humanity is called, once again, to bear the renewed image of God incarnate, Jesus. The image of Jesus's life, death, resurrection, and ascension is a recovering of something lost. And so, it is ultimately God's initiative and God's image that transforms us. The context of Isa 25:7–8 shows us that after that great day when God swallows death, there is great praise and celebration. Because it is God's doing, it may seem too far out of humanity's reach or power to make any change; to wait until that great day comes. However, the people still had to seek and learn God's righteousness. They waited and remained steadfast for God's salvation (Isa 25:9; 26:2–3). The same is true for Paul and his audience in 1 Cor 15. It is God who initiates the change, it is, after all, Christ's image we must reflect. Nevertheless, when we work to clothe ourselves with the image of the resurrected and ascended Christ, we have the hope and steadfast-assurance of "knowing that [our] struggle is not empty in the Lord" (1 Cor 15:58).

Continual practice of putting on the image of the resurrected and incorruptible Christ, is something Paul's audience would have understood to be progressively transformative. Paul's call to be steadfast and immovable (1 Cor 15:58) is a call to live in the present with salvation's story, both past and future in mind. The labor and struggle of living (present) a crucified and resurrected lifestyle (past and present) does not go unseen before the Lord (future judgement).

Instead, God's victory is accomplished through Christ (1 Cor 15:57); victory that will ultimately swallow up death. Paul, with understanding the reality of death, urges his audience to remain steadfast in God's mighty act, "in order to superabound in the work of the Lord" (1 Cor 15:58).

D. Conclusion

Because of humanity's disobedience, the clothing needs repair. Humanity has overworn the same clothing for too long. Paul urges the Corinthians to put on the clothing of Jesus, which is necessarily cruciform. Living a cruciform life, for the Corinthians, means they certainly have not reached the end stage of existence. On the contrary. Recovery of the image of God in Christ is discovered by "always excelling in the work of the Lord," through wearing the image of Jesus. This is accomplished through progressive stages, starting in the image of the first Adam. Humans must recognize its resemblance to the first Adam, but instead of staying stagnant, humanity must live into Jesus's example of life for others. Jesus is not super-human, he is image of true humanity. In order to bear the image of Christ, there must be a dying and rising (this is the heaven on earth experience) found when we embrace the fullness of humanity, both in the first and last Adam.

Tension is necessary for transformation; the new humanity, initiated in Christ, the heavenly one, is called to bear his image as a lifestyle change and work on putting on the resurrection body, as modelled by Christ, in incorruptibility and immortality. The image of the first Adam is not forgotten, instead God's original life-giving image is recovered in the last Adam, Christ. Jesus came to earth to show humanity how to truly live into the image of God; he came not necessarily as an alternative, but as the intended fullness of humanity. The ethics of the resurrection encompass the task laid out by living into the recovered image of God in Christ. The

task Christ laid out is not one that was readily accepted in Paul's time. Paul says, "for I decided to know nothing among you except Jesus Christ, and him crucified" (1 Cor 2:2; NRSV). For Paul, living into the image of God in Christ "and the power of his resurrection" is to share in his suffering "by becoming like him in his death, if somehow I may attain the resurrection from the dead" (Phil 3:10–11; NRSV). Paul also said something of Christ's life-giving nature and how he relates to Christ, saying, "I have been crucified with Christ...who loved me and gave himself for me" (Gal 2:19–20; NRSV). These verses setup Paul's second letter to the Corinthians.

Next, we will look at Paul's use of investiture language in 2 Cor 5:2–4 and how a misunderstanding of Paul's language can inhibit or even paralyze the audience. Paul's next mention of resurrection living, with the image of clothing, comes in the second letter to the Corinthians with clarifications of possible misunderstandings within the Corinthian church.

II. Investiture Language of 2 Corinthians 5

Paul's motivation for writing 2 Cor is commonly understood as a defense of his authority, as well as possibly Apollos and others. However, if we are still to think Paul wanted the Corinthians to imitate him (1 Cor 4:16; 11:1), then we should assume the lifestyle Paul is defending is one he continues to call the Corinthians to live when writing the 2 Cor as well. The context that surrounds the investiture language in 2 Cor 5:2–4 is especially important. Paul continues his conversation with the Corinthians about resurrection and cruciformity from 1 Cor 15 into 2 Cor 4–5.

We will start by looking at the phrase, πάντοτε τὴν νέκρωσιν τοῦ Ἰησοῦ ἐν τῷ σώματι περιφέροντες (at all times, bearing around the death of Jesus), in 2 Cor 4:10, along with its context of the transformation that takes place as part of bearing around the death of Jesus. Now

in 2 Cor 4, paired with Paul's understanding of what it means to bear the image of the heavenly one, Paul's message is nuanced and modelled more personally compared to 1 Cor 15:48–9. We will then explore how one bears the image of Jesus through carrying around his death supports the 'groaning for another dwelling while living in the present' that is found in 2 Cor 5:2–4. Next, we will dig into 2 Cor 5:1–5, which is the immediate context of the investiture language in verses 2–4. Finally, we will examine the ministry of reconciliation in 2 Cor 5:18–20 and how it relates to resurrection ethics.

A. Bearing the Death of Jesus in our Embodied Life (2 Corinthians 4:8–12, 16)

⁸In all things we are oppressed but not crushed, confused but not driven to despair, ⁹persecuted but not deserted, cast down but not destroyed. ¹⁰At all times we are bearing around the death of Jesus in the body, in order that, indeed, the life of Jesus may be revealed in our body. ¹¹For while we live we are being surrendered to death on account of Jesus, in order that, indeed, the life of Jesus may be revealed in our mortal flesh. ¹²Therefore, death is active in us, but life (is active) in you all. ¹⁶Therefore, we are not weak, and if indeed our outer person is being wasted away, although our inner person is being renewed day by day. (2 Cor 8–12, 16)

Paul speaks of sharing in Christ's death through a set of affliction, confusion, persecution, and being struck down (2 Cor 4:8–9). The next two verses (2 Cor 4:10–11) are reminiscent of the image of bearing Christ's image mentioned in 1 Cor 15:48–49. We carry around these things, always, so that new life is made visible (2 Cor 4:10–11). Bearing the image of Jesus in 1 Cor 15:49 is expanded upon in 2 Cor 4–5. The death of Jesus is now where Paul focuses his attention, understanding the life of a Christ follower is dangerous. Paul provides a rationale of this call to live a dangerous life. The call to bear the image of Christ (1 Cor 15:49) is a lifestyle of affliction, confusion, persecution, and getting struck down (2 Cor 4:8–9). Paul says that this deathly image is so that new life is made visible in the current, mortal flesh (2 Cor 4:11).

But, “do not lose heart,” Paul says, because this is a process of renewal. Suffering is part of the renewing transformation of carrying around the death of Jesus (2 Cor 4:10, 16). This is an expansion to Michael Gorman’s theology of cruciformity, which we will discuss at length below. It is a lifestyle marked with suffering, so that new life may be revealed. The outer nature is deteriorating away, when referring to clothing being eaten by moths. Let us look outside of Paul’s writings, into some of Jesus’s teachings in Luke 12. Exploring Jesus’s teaching on clothing and lifestyle change will illuminate Paul’s writing about clothing in 2 Cor 4–5, especially when clothing is linked to ethics.

Right in the midst of Jesus’s teachings on material goods and excessive wealth appears clothing imagery too helpful to our discussion on resurrection ethics to pass by. Jesus is talking about God’s provision for all creation, including humanity’s needs (Luke 12:28–31). Jesus encourages his audience not to be anxious of the future, but instead to seek the kingdom and God will continue to provide (Luke 12:31). So, what does this kingdom look like? It is a kingdom filled with people ready to sell their things and provide for the poor (Luke 12:33). This is where the deteriorating clothing imagery appears. Possessions and alms are to be given when purses and treasure are to be provided and kept safe, assuming the treasure and purse do not hold possessions or alms. Jesus calls his hearers to live a radical life for the sake of others. God will provide for you, as he does for all creation (12:27–28), therefore you are called to give away your possessions. This ethic is immersed in clothing imagery as well, gird yourself in service (12:35, 37). A way of life that reflects God’s goodness to all; a way of life that reflects God’s sacrifice for others.

In this next parable, Jesus speaks about staying alert and ready for when the master returns (Luke 12:34–48). The saying, “Jesus is coming, look busy” most likely has its roots in this passage from Luke. It is true, there are several passages that say the coming of the Son of Man (Jesus) will be unknown (cf. Matt 24:43; Luke 17:24; 1 Thess 5:2; Rev 3:3). This is the same apathetic lifestyle Jesus is warning against in these passages. When the master comes and sees his responsible servants working, the master in turns serves these faithful servants. Both the servants and the master act as servants (12:37). This is the beautiful image of the kingdom, filled with active members, living into their calling to serve others, both those whom you work for and those whom work for you.

The way of life described in Luke 12 starts with inner-renewal that is then lived out. This is similar to how Paul speaks in 2 Cor 4–5. A lifestyle of service is a human calling for all to clothe themselves with the clothes Jesus wore, clothes of life, death, and resurrection. A Lifestyle of service for others is filled with a continual process of death and resurrection. A lifestyle of service for others is a decision to be made everyday. It is not a passive lifestyle to assume (or fall asleep when asked to remain awake), as would be the way of bearing the image of the “dusty one” (1 Cor 15:49). While living in tension of the “already and not yet,” with the ultimate restoration of all things still on the horizon, Paul urges his audience to put on a resurrection lifestyle over their self. Paul seems to be clarifying his point on clothing and whether to get rid of the old stuff and replace everything, or to recover and put new clothing on over the old.

The resurrection, as a heavenly dwelling, is being put on over the body, as an outward sign of the inner-renewal of the person. This inner-renewal (2 Cor 4:16), however is not without distress. Distressed in every way (2 Cor 4:8), “always carrying in the body the death of Jesus” (2

Cor 4:10). This lifestyle is what Michael Gorman has called *cruciformity*.⁷⁵ Cruciformity is living a cross-shaped life, always carrying around the death of Jesus. This, however, is not the end of Paul's message, nor the gospel message. Paul claims that Jesus's death on a cross was not in vain. Jesus is raised from the dead and models a radically different way of living; service to others, through bearing around the death of Jesus, so that others may live (2 Cor 4:10).

The word περιφέροντες (to carry around or bear) in 2 Cor 4:10 is a compound of the verb φέρω (to carry/bear/lead) with the preposition περί (concerning, about, around) as a prefix. Followers of Jesus carry around his suffering and death so that life may be revealed in them. Modern readers typically misunderstand Paul's ancient rhetorical grammar in 2 Cor 4:10. While this is started in individuals, it is the community that fully reflects the recovered image of God in Christ. The life-giving image that is revealed is in "our [plural] body [singular]" (2 Cor 4:10). The suffering is not carried by the leadership of the church in Corinth, nor should the Senior Pastor of any contemporary church be the sole bearer of Jesus's death. It is a communal act; there is unity in the body (singular) of Christ, bore by many people (plural).

In the same way, resurrection living is not done in solitude instead it is shared in community. This sort of rhetoric may have been easily understood in Corinth, but it seems to be more complicated for modern readers to grasp the implicit communal grounding of bearing around the death of Jesus. As Michael Barram has said, bearing around the death of Jesus was in opposition with the Roman virtues of "wisdom, power, freedom, and knowledge, suggesting that an appropriate and faithful missional hermeneutic in the Corinthian context must be

⁷⁵ For more, see Gorman, *Cruciformity*.

characterized by foolishness, weakness, slavery, and love.”⁷⁶ Sacrificial life and care for others, particularly the outcasts of society, was more the norm of the beginning church in the book of Acts (cf. Acts 2:42–47; 4:32–37;). This lifestyle continued, with nuances into Paul’s writing to 2 Cor 8.⁷⁷

It seems to be a backward way to live one’s life and very much at odds with American exceptionalism. Our lives should manifest the life of Jesus through our suffering? This suffering is not something superficial or self-loathing. Instead, the suffering is for others, not ourselves or the church. Paul made this clear in 1 Cor 4:10–13 by saying that he and his companions suffered so that there might be life in others, there in the Corinthian community. This is Paul’s cruciformity, his pattern of dying with Christ as an integral part of Christian life and community. Gorman speaks of Paul’s “cruciform love” found in 2 Cor 4:7–12.⁷⁸ This love is for others; Jesus did not die for himself, he died for others, to show them the way of life. This is why Paul, in 2 Cor 4:10, refers to the dying of Jesus “as a prototype and paradigm of apostolic suffering.”⁷⁹ Calling back to Paul’s rhetoric in 1 Cor 15 when speaking on the first and last Adam’s purposes, the Corinthians would have seen Paul’s life-giving ethics modeled after the last Adam, Jesus who is the one who gives life to others (1 Cor 15:45). I further argue, this ethic of living is not for Paul and his disciples, but still an urging to the Corinthian community to live their life, modelled after Jesus. In 2 Cor 4, the suffering is also an incarnational example of how Paul and his

⁷⁶ Michael Barram, “‘Fools for the sake of Christ’: Missional Hermeneutics and Praxis in the Corinthian Correspondence,” in *Missiology: An International Review* 43/2 (2015): 198.

⁷⁷ See 2 Cor 8:13–15, when Paul harkens back to Exodus 16.

⁷⁸ Gorman, *Cruciformity*, 202.

⁷⁹ Gorman, *Cruciformity*, 86.

companions lived and wore the clothing of the recovered image of God in Christ. Paul calls his audience in 2 Cor 4–5, just as he did in 1 Cor 15:49, to carry on this lifestyle, this discipleship.

The words for bearing in 1 Cor 15:49 and 2 Cor 4:10 are very similar, φορέω (1 Cor 15:49) and περιφέρω (2 Cor 4:10). Paul, in 2 Cor, goes back to a more basic and well used word, φέρω, while also attaching a prefix, περί. This further nuances his message from an urging, “let us bear,” in 1 Cor 15:49, to an assumed way of life, “at all times we are bearing” in 2 Cor 4:10. Just as the calling in 1 Cor 15:49 was communal (hortatory subjunctive, ‘let us’), bearing the death of Jesus (so life may be revealed) is part of the church’s communal identity. So then, Paul does not call a select few to live lives worthy of the calling (Eph 4:1; Col 1:10). Instead his calling is a communal task, started in Jesus, modelled by Paul and his disciples. Then, it is lived out through a changed mode of being in daily life in Corinth. We will explore this changed mode of being in relation to Paul’s use of clothing imagery in Eph 4 and Col 3 in the next chapter.

Just as Paul urged his audience to bear/wear (φορέω) the image of Christ in 1 Cor 15:49, it is now an assumed part of daily life in 2 Cor 4:10. The link between bearing the image of Christ in 1 Cor 15:49 to the clothing imagery in 1 Cor 15:53–4 is expounded upon in 2 Cor 4–5. Bearing the image of Christ (1 Cor 15:49) is lived out by bearing the death of Jesus, daily, so that life will be made visible. Living life for others is marked by suffering and groaning. The groans of suffering are growing pains of transformation into the resurrection life.

B. *Inhabiting a Heavenly Dwelling: Metaphor for the Resurrection (2 Corinthians 5:1–5)*

For we know that if ever our earthly tent is destroyed we have a building from God, a house not made with hands, eternal in the heavens. ²For indeed we groan in this [earthly tent], longing to be further clothed with our dwelling from heaven; ³if, indeed when we have been unclothed we will not be found naked. ⁴For indeed, while being burdened in the tent, we groan because we do not wish to be unclothed but to be further clothed, in order that death might be swallowed up by life. ⁵Moreover, he who has prepared for us this, having given the deposit of the Spirit to us. (2 Cor 5:1–5)

Humanity does strive for a better existence, but we strive in our current state—our present life. We strive for an existence where mortality is swallowed up by life (2 Cor 5:4), by the same life-giving spirit, that is Jesus (1 Cor 15:45–47), who swallowed up death (1 Cor 15:54b). We long to thrive in new clothing, our new dwelling, prepared in heaven for our life on earth. Many have read 2 Cor 5:1–4 as other-worldly, but logically if we are groaning to be further clothed (2 Cor 5:2, 4), for something to be put on us, how can this be read as anything other than bodily and this-worldly? Because the origin of our new dwelling is prepared by God in heaven (2 Cor 5:1) it does not mean our destination is heaven. Michael Knowles points out that Paul says, “a physical existence [on earth] that is already good will ultimately be overlaid by something better.”⁸⁰ We should not mistake our destination with the origin of our dwelling. We groan in our earthly body. We groan to put on something better, not to go far away from earth. God’s love and desire for the redemption of this world, including all creation inhabiting it, is an overarching biblical theme that underlies Paul’s point in 2 Cor 4–5.⁸¹

⁸⁰ Michael P. Knowles, *We Preach Not Ourselves* (Grand Rapids: Brazos, 2008), 204.

⁸¹ This idea is found in Brian J. Walsh and J. Richard Middleton, *The Transforming Vision: Shaping a Christian World View* (Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity Press, 1984). This book has dramatically shaped my worldview and interpretation of Scripture.

Our whole self is not being replaced with something completely new, nor are we going far away from this place. No, we live into the hope of a heavenly dwelling, today. We groan for that end, but in our groaning and distress—living a cruciform life for others—we are better prepared for our work on this earth, mitigating unnecessary suffering.

Many in the modern church have misunderstood this passage from 2 Cor 5. It seems the Corinthian community had trouble understanding Paul's use of investiture language too. Maybe this is why Paul clarifies his investiture language from 1 Cor 15 in 2 Cor 4–5. Maybe they misunderstood what Paul meant to be clothed with the incorruptibility and immortality (1 Cor 15:53–54). They may have understood the body disrobing the heavy mortal flesh and bone; a split between the immortal soul and frail, other parts of a human life. This was the predominant worldview Paul was speaking into and affecting change.⁸² Because Paul did not use σῶμα (body) in 1 Cor 15:53–54 when speaking about the resurrection, maybe the Corinthian community misunderstood it as the ancient dualistic split of soul/body; the body being discarded and the immortal and incorruptible soul remaining.

Paul, during the second letter we have, uses ἐπενδύομαι (to put on over), a compound word found only in 2 Cor 5:2 and 4 from ἐνδύω (to put on) and ἐπί (on/over), in addition to his use of ἐνδύω elsewhere without the prefix, ἐπί. Paul's nuanced explanation of clothing enhances his past argument of acknowledging the history of the man of the dust in 1 Cor 15:45–49 but to bear the full image of humanity, found in Christ. Paul is saying he and his disciples have not stripped themselves but instead put on, in addition to their tarnished humanity, a coat (ἐπενδύτης) of

⁸² For more on this, see Craig Keener, *1–2 Corinthians* (Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2005), 179–180.

sorts.⁸³ Because the word is in the middle, the word is best translated as to be further clothed or “to put on one’s self in addition.”⁸⁴ Paul calls the community in Corinth to put on the dwelling over their current self so that “what is mortal may be swallowed up by life” (2 Cor 5:4b) instead of replacing the body with something else, say, an immortal soul—naked and unclothed without a body (2 Cor 5:4a).

The fact that Paul chose an intensification by using ἐπενδύομαι in 2 Cor 5:2 and 4 means the tent he inhabits is not necessarily bad, but something that needs radical transformation. The tent (2 Cor 5:4a) has become corrupt, disgraceful, weak, and just getting by by its mortal, ordinary nature (1 Cor 15:42–44). It is only through a further-clothing of life (that swallows up mortality), which is empowered by the Spirit of God, when radical transformation can take place. While Paul and his companions, as well as the Corinthians, wait for the further-clothed body, groaning along the way, they are given a comforter, God’s Spirit (2 Cor 5:5).

God sent his Spirit “having given the deposit of the Spirit to us” (2 Cor 5:5). We have confidence in God’s Spirit, yet still recognize the tension between life now and the future resurrection body. With the deposit of a better life, our resurrection through the Spirit, we are called to live a holy life, which is judged by our actions in the body (2 Cor 5:10). The deposit should inspire humanity to live into the recovered image of God, in daily life. The same recovered image that is marked by a life of suffering for other’s sake, modeled by Jesus (2 Cor 4:10).

⁸³ The contemporary church needs this holistic understanding of clothing and ethics.

⁸⁴ William D. Mounce, *The Analytical Lexicon to the Greek New Testament* (Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 2013), 201.

The heavenly dwelling, put on over, is initiated by God's own Spirit, working in and through the lives of humanity. As a foretaste of the resurrection, the life-giving power of the Spirit is the foretaste of the new clothing. The Spirit has tabernacled in Paul and guides himself and companions toward a sacrificial life for the Corinthians. The community's life is then radically changed, in turn becoming life-giving for others. New creation has come (2 Cor 5:17)! Transformation continues moving forward, day by day, toward the renewal of all things. The Spirit's deposit is empowering for all humanity, since Paul next calls the Corinthians to consider the radical idea of reconciliation. There is redemption and freedom in the task Paul and his companions have modelled for the Corinthians. The message of reconciliation, as we will explore next, is a way of life that gives life to others (1 Cor 15:45–49) and swallows up death and mortality (1 Cor 15:44; 2 Cor 5:4).

C. Ambassadors of Reconciliation on Behalf of Jesus (2 Corinthians 5:18–20)

¹⁸All this is from God, who reconciled us to himself through Christ, and has given us the ministry of reconciliation; ¹⁹that is, in Christ God was reconciling the world to himself, not counting their trespasses against them, and entrusting the message of reconciliation to us. ²⁰So we are ambassadors for Christ, since God is making his appeal through us; we entreat you on behalf of Christ, be reconciled to God. (2 Cor 5:18–20)

Paul's message of reconciliation is not only encouragement for a better world (2 Cor 5:19a), but a life Paul feels called to (2 Cor 5:18, 19b). "The love of Christ urges us on" and entrusts us with the message of reconciliation (2 Cor 5:14, 19). The ministry of reconciliation (2 Cor 5:18–20) must be read in context of the greater conversation on being further-clothed with a resurrection life (2 Cor 5:2–4) that is always carrying around the death of Jesus (2 Cor 4:10).

The spreading ministry of reconciliation is a natural outcome of fearing the Lord (2 Cor 5:11) and knowing the power Christ has in reconciling the world to Godself (2 Cor 5:18–20).

Paul is writing powerful words as an example and encouragement for a better way to live. The community must be equipped with the right clothing (2 Cor 5:4) for them to be ambassadors of Christ (2 Cor 5:20). God's Spirit dwells with the people, "as a deposit," who clothes and prepares creation for the restoration of all things.

The new creation (2 Cor 5:17) is God-initiated (2 Cor 5:18a) because of Christ's life, death, and resurrection (2 Cor 5:18b). Because new creation has come, the community is responsible to live a certain way (2 Cor 5:18c). The lifestyle the community lives is not one that looks inward, but one that looks to the "other" to break down the labels implicit in the "us versus them" mentality. The message of reconciliation is a message of "us for them" rather than "us versus them."⁸⁵ The reconciliation that happens is not a quick fix, however, in the life of the community. The gospel message (ministry of reconciliation) resonates a deep truth in community life that yearns for a new way of living. The ministry of reconciliation is at the core of the resurrection life Paul is exemplifying for the Corinthian community. Frank Rees rightly reflects on Jürgen Moltmann's writing, and says, "Moltmann seems to imply that resurrection life...relates to all creation."⁸⁶ Resurrection life is God, through Christ, reconciling the world to Godself (2 Cor 5:19). Moltmann's fuller picture of resurrection makes this point well.

Examining the word Paul uses for reconciliation should help us understand ethics more clearly. The word Paul uses for reconciliation (*καταλλάσσω*) appears only in the New Testament letters of Rom, and the Corinthian correspondence. *Καταλλάσσω* pairs *κατά* (according) with the

⁸⁵ Gungor, "Us For Them" on *One Wild Life: Soul* (Hither & Yon Records), 2015.

⁸⁶ Frank Rees, "Resurrection as Good News for the Poor: A Critical Appraisal of the Resurrection Theology of Jürgen Moltmann," in *Prophecy and Passion: Essays in Honour of Athol Gill* (ed. David Neville; Adelaide, Australia: Australian Theological Forum), 2002, 131.

verb, ἀλλάσσω (to change), which is seen in the greater Pauline corpus and once in the book of Acts.⁸⁷ With this, let us walk through 2 Cor 5:18–20. “And all things from God, having [changed us according] to Godself through Christ, also having given us the ministry of [changing according to Godself], since, just as God was [changing the world] according to Godself in Christ, not counting our sins, and having put the word of [change according to Godself] into us. So, therefore, we are ambassadors of Christ, just as God is exhorting through us, we implore because of Christ, [change according] to God” (2 Cor 5:18–20). The change, maybe in likeness, has already started, when God “was reconciling the world to Godself in Christ” (19).

The radical change that is associated with following Christ was often times resisted, as seen in Luke’s account of Stephen’s arrest, speech, and stoning in Acts 6:14, where καταλλάσσω is used. Those in charge were afraid of the change wrapped up in the life of Jesus when compared to the customs of Moses (Acts 6:14).

What Jesus did was for the benefit for the Jewish people, as Stephen was trying to convey. What God did through Jesus was for the benefit of the world (κόσμος), not just a select few, and not only for humanity, but instead all of creation. God’s ministry of reconciliation is not only for Paul and his companions, but, “as we work together with him, we urge you also not to accept the grace of God in vain” (2 Cor 6:1; NRSV).

This task, initiated daily by putting on new clothes, bears a total change in how one lives. Moreover, “we must all appear before the judgment seat of the Lord, in order that each might receive the things done through the body according to what was done, whether good or bad” (2 Cor 5:10). Yet, through Christ’s reconciling power, our sins are not counted against us (2 Cor

⁸⁷ See Acts 6:14.

5:19) and this further empowers us to become ambassadors of Christ. This message that empowers us to live is the same message humanity proclaims to all creation. God is reconciling the world to Godself through an invitation, made through humanity (2 Cor 5:20). This is a central element of what it means to be made in the image of God; a prism of sorts, mediating God's presence on earth to all creation.⁸⁸

As ambassadors of Christ, living daily for others, through bearing the death of Jesus, new life is revealed because of, as Gorman has said, the "cruciform resurrection power" that is found in the new clothing.⁸⁹ Recovering the image of God in Christ and continually living into the life-giving Spirit requires God's people to put away the habits of the flesh and put on a new person, "created according to God in true equity and holiness" (Eph 4:24).

D. Conclusion

For the children of God to work towards the redemption of all things, as groaned for by creation in Rom 8, there must be a dangerous change in the lives of humanity. Paul's call to bear the death of Jesus is a dangerous calling, one that necessitates suffering. Suffering is part of the cruciform transformation into the resurrection of creation. This is only accomplished by the power of the same Spirit who raised Jesus from the dead (Rom 8:11–12). The Spirit of God dwells with us so that the image of God in Christ can be recovered. This recovered image is one that came to earth, dwelt, and suffered death so that life may be given to all. Life for others is what Paul frames the message of reconciliation around. Resurrection ethics is, therefore, a changing of one's lifestyle toward others, so that all, others included, may live.

⁸⁸ For more on this, see J. Richard Middleton, *The Liberating Image: The Imago Dei in Genesis 1* (Grand Rapids: Brazos, 2005), 90.

⁸⁹ Gorman, *Inhabiting the Cruciform God*, 151.

The next chapter will take a closer look at two letters at least written in a similar Pauline line of thinking, Eph and Col. These two letters are filled with explicit ethical changes that happen because of Christ's resurrection and believer's living into that resurrection.

CHAPTER 2

UNETHICAL AND ETHICAL BEHAVIORS: RESURRECTION LIFE IN EPHESIANS AND COLOSSIANS

Paul in 1 and 2 Cor framed his message of resurrection ethics around anthropology by highlighting the change in nature of the resurrection body. 1 Cor 15 addresses the roots that the new humanity has in creation (1 Cor 15:45–47) while focusing on a changed way to be truly human, manifested in the last Adam, who is Christ (1 Cor 15:48–49). Paul reaches the pinnacle of his message, using clothing language to describe how the new humanity will finally put on immortality and incorruptibility (1 Cor 15:53–54). Paul then proclaims a final ethical exhortation for the new humanity to practice life because of Christ’s eschatological fulfillment of humanity (1 Cor 15:55–58).

Paul builds on his message in 2 Cor 4–5 on the anthropological foundation in 1 Cor 15. 2 Cor implies an ethic must come from putting on the heavenly dwelling “in order that death might be swallowed up by life” (2 Cor 5:4; my own translation). Paul, in building on this anthropological base, finishes 2 Cor 5 with an explicit ethical exhortation to be ministers of reconciliation (2 Cor 5:18–20). So, the first way to describe the resurrection life is laid out in Paul’s correspondence with the Corinthians. Paul uses investiture language embedded in anthropological images where the new humanity puts on immortality and incorruptibility (1 Cor 15), and works to bring reconciliation to all creation (2 Cor 5).

It is now time to examine the second Pauline way to describe the resurrection life. There are two sections in each Eph and Col, which speak of ethical behaviors that use language similar to that found in the Corinthian correspondence. Eph and Col assume the anthropological foundation laid out in the Corinthian correspondence but focus on the ethical outcome by the

new humanity, thus describing the second way of the resurrection life, that is, the ethical replacing the unethical behaviors. The second way of describing the resurrection life produces a coherent alternative praxis.

For the purposes of this thesis, I will not dive deeply into the debate on authorship of these two disputed letters because who actually penned the letters is not interesting nor does it concern the substance of this thesis as a whole. The language is thoroughly Pauline, so I will refer to author of Eph and Col as Paul. I do, however, want to raise a question at the outset about the differences between how Paul presents his message of practicing a resurrection life in the Corinthian correspondence and the letters to the Ephesians and Colossians, thus leading to two ways of describing the resurrection life.

The question that interests me pertaining to the difference is this: why does Paul shift his clothing imagery to taking things off (Eph 4:22, 25; Col 3:9) contrasted to putting clothing on over (2 Cor 5) and not disregarding the first Adam or ordinary nature (1 Cor 15)? I will address this question by exploring the differences in Paul's message to the Ephesians and Colossians versus that in the Corinthian correspondence, specifically the list of ethical behaviors attached to clothing imagery in Eph and Col.

Perhaps Paul, in Eph and Col, is targeting the specific negative practices in the community's lifestyle, for example, emptiness of mind (Eph 4:17), darkness in understanding, alienation from God, ignorance, hardness of heart (4:18), licentiousness, greed, and impurity (4:19). These practices are from the former way of life, part of the former community ethic. The former way of life is described each in Eph 4:17–21 and Col 3:5, 8–9. Paul calls the church in Ephesus and Colossae to take off these specific acts. The community is not left naked and

unclothed (2 Cor 5:3–4), not even for a time. The community ethic is to be replaced with a new set of practices. Practicing the old ways does not represent the new humanity. The old community ethic represents the old humanity (Eph 4:22–23; Col 3:9). The new community ethic more fully mirrors the image of God (Eph 4:24; Col 3:10). So, why is there a difference in how Paul communicates the ethics of the resurrection to the Corinthians and Ephesians and Colossians?

In the Corinthian correspondence, Paul addresses life and death, mortality putting on immortality, and the paradox within this transformation, which is bearing the death of Jesus so that new life may be found. The ethics of the resurrection in the Corinthian correspondence is two-part. Paul, in 1 Cor addresses anthropology through his use of the first and last Adam (1 Cor 15:45–49) where ethics are subsidiary and only explicitly appear at two places (1 Cor 15:49, 58). 2 Cor builds the anthropology addressed in 1 Cor (2 Cor 5:1–4) and spotlights the paradoxical lifestyle that comes with a changed way of living, which is modeled by sacrificial love for others (2 Cor 5:11–21). The Corinthian correspondence is more focused on anthropology, contrasting the old humanity with the new humanity (1 Cor 15:55–57; 2 Cor 5:17). The Corinthian correspondence focuses more on the starting point of humanity and what eventually became of it through perpetual disobedience and violence to God and all creation (2 Cor 5:19). The new humanity, found in Christ is not something completely different from the first Adam. But because of resistance and disobedience, the generations following the first Adam drifted away from the intended image-representation that is fully revealed in the last Adam, Christ. Let us now take a closer look at the second Pauline way to describe the ethics of the resurrection, starting in Eph 4.

I. Investiture Language of Ephesians 4

The words Paul uses to describe the resurrection life are the following: ἀποθέσθαι, “to put away” (Eph 4:22, 25), ἀπεκδυσάμενοι, “to take off” (Col 3:9), ἐνδύσω, “to clothe” (1 Cor 15:53–4; 2 Cor 5:2–4; Eph 4:24; Col 3:10, 12), ἀνανεόομαι, “to renew/renovate” (found only in Eph 4:23), along with an interchangeable word, ἀνακαινόω, “to renew” (2 Cor 4:16; Col 3:10).

Paul leads up to his discussion of investiture in Eph by describing a way of life contrary to that of Jesus (Eph 4:17–21), behaviors and practices that Paul will warn his audience to put off (Eph 4:25–32). This is the gentile pattern of living, which is not for followers of the Lord (Eph 4:20). Verses 17–19 describe how gentiles live; they contain a list of behaviors that followers of the Lord should not practice. The three indicative verbs in verses 20 and 21 are learned (ἐμάθετε), heard (ἠκούσατε), and were taught (ἐδιδάχθητε). These verbs are the foundation of the investiture language because how the community was taught, by hearing and learning, is fleshed out by the specific ethical behaviors the community is called to replace with unethical behaviors. Paul gives an ethical backbone to living a renewed and resurrected life.

Once Paul affirms the new humanity (with Christ as its head; Eph 4:15–19), he moves on to describe specifically how to live this out in daily life, the ethics of the resurrection (Eph 4:20–32). The new community ethic continues into Eph 5, specifically 5:1–5, where Paul uses the conjunction οὖν as a final segue into a command to be imitators of God (Eph 5:1); this command mirrors his investiture language in 4:24. Let us start with Paul’s description of what a life contrary to Christ looks like.

A. *Previous Behaviors as Contrary to Christ (Ephesians 4:17–21)*

¹⁷Now this I affirm and insist on in the Lord: you must no longer live as the Gentiles live, in the futility of their minds. ¹⁸They are darkened in their understanding, alienated from the life of God because of their ignorance and hardness of heart. ¹⁹They have lost all sensitivity and have abandoned themselves to licentiousness, greedy to practice every kind of impurity. ²⁰That is not the way you learned Christ! ²¹For surely you have heard about him and were taught in him, as truth is in Jesus. (Eph 4:17–21; NRSV)

Different types of gentile-like behaviors are listed in this section (Eph 4:17–21), then later contrasted with a flourishing community in Eph 4:25–32. Paul reminds the Ephesians of how they used to live. They used to live depraved lives with minds filled with futility (Eph 4:17). The gentiles had a darkened understanding of life, and in turn were “alienated from the life of God because of the ignorance that is in them and the stubbornness of their heart” (Eph 4:18). The description in verses 17 and 18 comes immediately after Paul speaks about the body of Christ working together, “building itself up in love” (Eph 4:15–16). Paul describes gentile behaviors as blind, greedy, and insensitive (Eph 4:18–19). These kinds of practices break down communities instead of building them up. Paul pits sensitivity against abandonment (Eph 4:19), a sensitivity that allows the community to “speak the truth in love” and keep the body whole and connected (Eph 4:15–16). The gentiles have abandoned this sensitivity and oriented themselves to the sinful way of life, which is not the way of Christ (Eph 4:20). Paul knows that the Ephesian community has heard the message of Christ, and claims the life he described (Eph 4:17–19) is not what was taught to them (Eph 4:20–21).

The truth that was taught to the community is laid out in the following verses. Paul uses three verbs to communicate an alternative way of life to the Ephesian community; they have learned (ἐμάθετε) Christ, heard (ἠκούσατε) about him, and were taught (ἐδιδάχθητε) in him (Eph 4:20–21). Practicing the old behaviors is not the way you learned Christ (ἐμάθετε), therefore,

they should take off the old humanity and the behaviors associated with it. Another use of ἐμάθετε occurs in Col 1:7, which speaks of learning (ἐμάθετε)⁹⁰ the gospel that is spreading around the world (Col 1:5–7).

Harold W. Hoehner points out that the three infinitives in Eph 4:22–24 (ἀποθέσθαι (to put off/away), ἀνανεοῦσθαι (to renew/renovate), and ἐνδύσασθαι (to clothe/put on)) relate back to the verb ἐδιδάχθητε (you were taught) in verse 21.⁹¹ Hoehner draws from Buist M. Fanning’s, *Verbal Aspects*, saying both “putting off” and “putting on” are urgent actions and the second infinitive (ἀνανεοῦσθαι (to renew/renovate)) is in the present tense exhorting his audience to continually renew their minds by the spirit. The change in ethics that leads to transformation takes time and Fanning puts it, “must be continually acted upon and transferred from the realm of the potential to the actual.”⁹²

B. Transformation into the Renewed Image of God (Ephesians 4:22–24)

²²You were taught to put away your former way of life, your old self, corrupt and deluded by its lusts, ²³and to be renewed in the spirit of your minds, ²⁴and to clothe yourselves with the new self, created according to the likeness of God in true righteousness and holiness. (Eph 4:22–24; NRSV)

Paul urges the community to renew their minds (continually), which is being filled with the spirit instead of, as Frank Thielman put it, “intrinsic human habits.” Contrary to Thielman, these are not intrinsic to humanity but instead sinful. The former way of life is a choice to follow the sinful footsteps of fallen humanity, not some sort of original sin notion. Instead, Paul is

⁹⁰ The verb is identical to Eph 4:20’s use of μανθάνω.

⁹¹ Harold, W. Hoehner, *Ephesians: An Exegetical Commentary* (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2002), 599.

⁹² Buist M. Fanning, *Verbal Aspect in New Testament Greek* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1990), 360.

urging the Ephesian community to put into practice behaviors that God intended his creation to live by, as Thielman circles back to after saying the former ways of life are intrinsic to humanity.⁹³ The habits to be taken off are the sinful ways of living, practices that are contrary and disobedient to God and other (Eph 4:22–23). Both φθειρόμενον (being corrupted/ruined) and ἀνανεοῦσθαι (to renew) are in the present. Thielman says that these two words are in contrast to each other, saying “Paul’s readers are no longer on a self-destructive and ultimately ruinous path but are experiencing continual renewal.”⁹⁴ This beckons back to the Corinthian correspondence when Paul tells them to put on the image of Christ, continually bearing the image of Christ (1 Cor 15:48–49). Paul’s point is that there is a different way of living, contrary to a life of corruption, both to self and other. Corruption can lead to destruction because practicing the sinful life (Eph 4:18–19, 22) allows room for the devil (Eph 4:27) and does not build up the community (Eph 4:29).

Most modern translations, including the NRSV, aid the hyper-individualistic cultural understanding of salvation and ethics by translating “person” or “self” from ἄνθρωπον. By contrast the NET and KJV translate ἄνθρωπον as “man,” which at least gets at the collective sense of the word (even in its dated use). Most modern translations, in their translation of ἄνθρωπον, miss what Paul is saying here about transforming community life into the resurrection lifestyle in the present.⁹⁵ I will be translating τὸν παλαιὸν ἄνθρωπον and τὸν καινὸν ἄνθρωπον as

⁹³ Frank Thielman, *Ephesians* (Baker Exegetical Commentary on the New Testament; Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2010), 303–304.

⁹⁴ Thielman, *Ephesians*, 305.

⁹⁵ The NIV, NRSV, ESV, and CEB all translate ἄνθρωπον not as a collective singular, even when the context is explicitly communal and plural.

“the old humanity” and “the new humanity,” as Middleton has done (Eph 4:22, 24).⁹⁶ These translations fit the context and overall message that Paul makes in using the three plural indicatives (ἐμάθετε—you all learned; ἠκούσατε—you all heard; and ἐδιδάχθητε—you all were taught) in verses 20–21, which setup the communal investiture language.

The choice Paul puts before the Ephesians is that they can continue in the way that leads to corruption (Eph 4:22) or choose what is right and holy (Eph 4:24), which is pursued by the continual renewing of the mind (Eph 4:23). Paul calls the Ephesians to participate in taking off the old humanity (along with its habits) and put on the new humanity (both of which are middle infinitives in Eph 4:23–24). The corruption and renewal (Eph 4:22b–23a) are both in present and passive form. Corruption is part of what the ordinary nature. This is perpetuated throughout the generations without much activity, other than acceptance. The activity is seen in the second present passive word, ἀναεοῦσθαι. The old humanity can be accepted as part of life, but it ultimately leads to corruption (Eph 4:22). The new clothes can also be accepted as part of life (Eph 4:24). This choice requires a renovation of the mind (Eph 4:23). The new set of clothes (new humanity) is created by God and after God’s pattern, and humanity is called to put on the new clothing. God creates the clothing and the Spirit sustains (through the renewing of the mind) but humanity initiates the change, taking off the old habits and putting on the new humanity, which is modeled after God’s justice and holiness (Eph 4:24b).

Let us further explore the specific language in Eph 4:22–24, and its use outside Eph and Col, so we can more fully understand the argument Paul makes here. The “old humanity” is the

⁹⁶ Middleton, *A New Heaven and a New Earth*, 69.

same phrase Paul uses in Rom 6:6.⁹⁷ Rom 6 sets up a pattern of cruciform living similar to that found in the Corinthian correspondence.⁹⁸ Paul, in Eph 4 (and later Col 3), directly ties explicit ethical implications to the pattern. Rom 6 speaks of the death that occurs in the person's crucifixion with Jesus, so that they are slave to sin no more (Rom 6:6). The old humanity is being corrupted (Eph 4:22). This is the same phrase Paul uses in Col 3:9. Humanity is easily corrupted and in turn gets worn out. Because God's "true equity and holiness" are not easy to live into (Eph 4:24), it is no wonder why the same ordinary and corrupting habits are perpetuated, as if it is inevitably (and simply) human nature to sin and get worn out. But a renovated mind and a new humanity is possible and supposed to be practiced. The new humanity is a reflection of the renovated people, sustained by the Spirit of God.

The new humanity (Eph 4:24) is part of the larger body of Christ (Eph 4:15–16, 25). The community is to have one mind renovated by the Spirit (Eph 4:23). The word for renovate/renew is ἀνανεοῦσθαι. This is the only usage in the New Testament. However, it appears ten times in the LXX, all with the same general meaning, "to renew."^{99,100}

Paul calls the community, collectively, in Ephesus to have one, single mind. Just as the "you" in verse 22 is plural (ὕμᾱς), so is the "your" in verse 23 (ὕμῶν). I have appreciation for the older, more formal translations of the text that use "ye" when translating ὑμᾱς (22). The community in Ephesus, in turn, is called to live in such a way that reflects the likeness of God

⁹⁷ The phrase in Rom 6:6 (ὁ παλαιὸς ἄνθρωπος) is in the Nominative case, opposed to the Accusative in Eph 4:22 (τὸν παλαιὸν ἄνθρωπον).

⁹⁸ The cruciform way of life is covered in the chapter before this on 1 and 2 Cor.

⁹⁹ The word in Eph 4:23 is from ἀνανεόω, which is found in the following LXX passages: Job 33:24; Esth 13:2; 1 Macc 12:1, 3, 10, 16; 14:18, 22; 15:17; 4 Macc 18:4.

¹⁰⁰ Later, we will examine the parallel passage in Col 3:10 when Paul uses ἀνακαινύμενον (synonymous with ἀνανεοῦσθαι) and how the passages relate.

because of their (plural) renovated mind (singular; Eph 4:23). This is done because individual parts of the community clothe themselves with a new humanity, renewed in the image of God, which is revealed in Jesus (Eph 4:24). This renewal is a communal awareness and reaction to the life-giving Spirit of God.

The modern, “one-and-done” salvation model does not take Paul’s message of an ever-transforming resurrection lifestyle into account. It takes time to work toward holiness. Because the body is equipped with the right clothes, being right and holy in the world is attainable. But these qualities are not easy to attain, nor are they put on once. A daily renewal and renovation of the individuals inside a community, is required for transformation to occur.

C. The Specific Behaviors of Sharing Life Together (Ephesians 4:25—5:2)

²⁵So then, putting away falsehood, let all of us speak the truth to our neighbors, for we are members of one another. ²⁶Be angry but do not sin; do not let the sun go down on your anger, ²⁷and do not make room for the devil. ²⁸Thieves must give up stealing; rather let them labor and work honestly with their own hands, so as to have something to share with the needy. ²⁹Let no evil talk come out of your mouths, but only what is useful for building up, as there is need, so that your words may give grace to those who hear. ³⁰And do not grieve the Holy Spirit of God, with which you were marked with a seal for the day of redemption. ³¹Put away from you all bitterness and wrath and anger and wrangling and slander, together with all malice, ³²and be kind to one another, tenderhearted, forgiving one another, as God in Christ has forgiven you. ^{5:1}Therefore be imitators of God, as beloved children, ²and live in love, as Christ loved us and gave himself up for us, a fragrant offering and sacrifice to God. (Eph 4:25—5:2; NRSV)

In the following verses, Paul lists what this new humanity, clothed in a renewed image of God, looks like. After Paul reminds his audience that they are to clothe themselves in the new humanity (22–24), an action that requires both diligence and endurance, he gives a set of practical behaviors for them to live by. The remaining verses of chapter 4 list behaviors that the individual and community, clothed with the new humanity, are to practice. Paul gives sets

supporting reason for each set of ethical behavior. These behaviors reorient the community's relationships back to a flourishing lifestyle, back to the original intent for creation.

There is continuity with the body of Christ. The body of Christ is interconnected because (ὅτι) followers of Christ are part of one another (Eph 4:25). The community, with new clothing, "promotes the body's growth in building itself up in love" (Eph 4:16; NRSV). Verses 25–32 lay out five specific areas of life that are rooted in the change in humanity (Eph 4:22–24), starting with the first part of Paul's message in verse 25, "Therefore, putting away falsehood, speak the truth with those close by, because we are members of one another" (Eph 4:25; my own translation). The specific behaviors listed in Eph 4:25–32 lay out a daily ethic that is part of the Christian community. The corrupt community ethics are to be taken off (Eph 4:25), just as Paul exhorts the community to take off the old humanity and replace it with the new humanity (Eph 4:22–24).

Paul now explains τὴν προτέραν ἀναστροφὴν (the previous behaviors) that are part of the corrupt, old humanity (Eph 4:22). The detailed ethics of the community (Eph 4:25–32) all connect back to the new humanity being "created according to God in true equity and holiness" (Eph 4:24). Paul supports each behavior with a rationale. Why must the truth be spoken to each other? Because we are all part of one another (Eph 4:25). Falsehood creates walls of distrust that distances members of the community. Falsehood is part of the previous way of life, "which is being corrupted by the desires of deceit" (Eph 4:22) and does not represent the image of God "in true righteousness and holiness" (Eph 4:24b).

The second reason for a changed community ethic is about how to deal with anger. While the community works toward "true righteousness and holiness," members will get angry with

other members. Paul expects this and reassures his audience with healthy habits. The new humanity should reflect Christ's grace and mercy as best as possible. Paul calls the Ephesians to deal with conflict in a civil and timely manner (Eph 4:26). The message of verses 26–27 is motivation for a community to live in harmony. Why must a community not sin in anger? Because a community that does not deal with its angry feelings quickly “makes room for the devil” (Eph 4:26–27). The ethics are clear; honest communication within a community transforms its longevity and increases its “true righteousness and holiness” (Eph 4:24b).

The third part of Paul's message on community ethics has to do with his call to those who steal. Why should thieves give up stealing and work instead? Because they have something to give back to the community. They “labor and work honestly with their own hands, so as to (ἵνα) have something to share with the needy” (Eph 4:29; NRSV). The former way of life (Eph 4:22), the selfish and greedy practice of the gentiles (Eph 4:19) is transformed into work for others (Eph 4:28). The old clothing of the old humanity is being repurposed for the flourishing of the community, especially for those with the greatest need. Part of the reason there are those in need is because people with power, hoard it and do not share their knowledge and resources. “But that is not how you learned Christ” (Eph 4:20).

The fourth part of Paul's message on community ethics addresses the need to build members up (Eph 4:29a). Why must the individual and community, clothed with the new humanity, speak words that build each other up? In order that (ἵνα) “your (plural) words may give grace to those who hear” (Eph 4:29b). Words are powerful, and the responsibility of the new humanity is to build up with words of grace to all who hear.

The fifth and final part of Paul’s message on community ethics, rooted in the new humanity is found in verses 31–32. The individual and community, clothed with the new humanity, is called to lift up and put away “all bitterness and wrath and anger and wrangling and slander, together with all malice” (Eph 4:31; NRSV). Instead, they are called to “be kind to one another, tenderhearted, forgiving one another, just as (καθὼς) God in Christ has forgiven you” (Eph 4:32).

Paul’s message on community ethics is laid out in five parts, each relating back to “putting away your former way of life” and “cloth[ing] yourselves with the new humanity,” all which points to the creator God who made humanity to live righteous and holy lives (Eph 4:22–24; NRSV, adapted). These are very explicit behaviors the individual and community, clothed with the new humanity, are called to practice. These practices are part of the continual renewal (Eph 4:23), as eighteen out of twenty-three verbals are in the present form.¹⁰¹ These five parts revolve around an ethic of community flourishing, as God intended from the beginning. Practicing the ethics of the resurrection is an choice the community must make on a daily basis, as living for the other does not come naturally. Paul explains this in the final section of our exploration in Eph.

A community that imitates God and exudes Christ’s love is a community that is clothed with the new humanity. Paul continues his pronouncements of ethical behaviors in Eph 5:1–5, behaviors that reflect the new humanity. Paul ties Christ’s loving sacrifice to how the new humanity is supposed to live (Eph 5:1–2). Imitating Christ’s sacrificial love intensifies the

¹⁰¹ Only five of the twenty-three verbals are not present form in verses 25–32, including ἐσφραγίσθητε (you have been sealed), which seems to refer back to an act in the past, most likely the Christ-event.

behavior the new humanity must initiate. There is no passive sacrificial love. There is active, intentional love, to and for others; this is what Christ modeled for all humanity.

II. Investiture Language of Colossians 3

The rich, Pauline ethical urging of the community is also found in the letter to the Colossians. The language in each section on investiture language in Eph and Col are similar. This next section will focus on the investiture language contained in Col 3. Col 3 starts with the phrase, “so if you have been raised with Christ...” (Col 3:1a). The resurrection language sets the tone for the whole chapter. Col 3:1a follows from to 2:20, “if with Christ you died,” answering it with positive motivation for the audience. Paul starts this chapter with a plea to live changed lives because of the resurrection; the resurrection his audience has in Christ. What does this community, which shares in Christ’s resurrection, look like? It is a community that chooses a higher way of life, one that focuses on “things that are above, where Christ is” (Col 3:1b). The community practices an ethic that puts to death what is not from above, that is, what is Christ-like.

After Paul provides two vice-lists (Col 3:5, 8) the community is to “put to death” (Col 3:5a) he sums it up in verse 9, saying “do not lie to one another” (Col 3:9a). Paul does not leave the community without standards, but instead tells them how to put on a new ethical standard (Col 3:10). The new ethical standard, rooted in their resurrection with Christ, is being realized because of the transformation that takes place with the new set of clothing (Col 3:10–14). The message Paul makes here in Col 3 uses very similar language, sometimes identical phrases to make his point clear. That is the unethical behaviors are to be taken off and a new community ethic is to be practiced. The investiture language is surrounded by cruciform language (Col 2:20;

3:1, 5). The resurrection life is one that takes on practices that are contrary to the disobedient ways the Colossians “once followed” (Col 3:7). The alternative practice of the resurrection life is possible because the community must die to its former way of doing things and be raised with Christ. This is the paradox of the cruciform resurrection life.

A. *Raised with Christ Means Putting to Death a Life of Vices (Colossians 3:1–8)*

¹So if you have been raised with Christ, seek the things that are above, where Christ is, seated at the right hand of God. ²Set your minds on things that are above, not on things that are on earth, ³for you have died, and your life is hidden with Christ in God. ⁴When Christ who is your life is revealed, then you also will be revealed with him in glory. ⁵Put to death, therefore, whatever in you is earthly: fornication, impurity, passion, evil desire, and greed (which is idolatry). ⁶On account of these the wrath of God is coming on those who are disobedient. ⁷These are the ways you also once followed, when you were living that life. ⁸But now you must get rid of all such things—anger, wrath, malice, slander, and abusive language from your mouth. (Col 3:1–8; NRSV)

Being raised with Christ is central to understanding the investiture language found in Col 3:9–12. The location of Christ is also important to understand Paul’s way of communicating to the Colossians. As Andrew Lincoln said, the author of Col sees “the starting point and source of the believer’s life in the resurrected Christ in heaven, from where it works itself out in earthly life and from where it will eventually be publicly revealed.”¹⁰² Middleton has named this the “apocalyptic pattern.”¹⁰³ Paul calls his audience to live by a higher standard; focus on the things above (Col 3:2). Living as the gentiles did (Eph 4:17) is a worldly standard (Col 3:2). The community has died to that kind of lifestyle (Col 3:3) and has set their “minds on things from above” (Col 3:2; NRSV).

¹⁰² Andrew T. Lincoln, “The Letter to the Colossians,” in *The New Interpreter’s Bible* (Nashville TN: Abingdon, 2000), 11:638.

¹⁰³ Middleton, *A New Heaven and a New Earth*, 212, ff.

When Paul begins his first list of vices in Col 3, he directly implores the community to “Put to death...whatever in you is earthly” (Col 3:5; NRSV). This command to “put to death” earthly vices (Col 3:5) is something that the community continued to battle with, even after being raised with Christ. Life in Christ is not a passive life, but an active, initiative-filled practice of putting certain habits to death, perhaps daily (cf. 1 Cor 15:31). Both “seek” (ζητεῖτε) and “put to death” (νεκρώσατε) are active verbs that the community is the subject of. Paul then lists vices that do not “promote the body’s growth in building itself up in love” (Eph 4:16; NRSV). The second list of vices is prefaced by another command, “put off” (Col 3:8a). This is the same word Paul uses in Eph 4:22 and 25 when imploring the Ephesians to “take off your previous behavior” including “putting away falsehood” (Eph 4:22, 25). The second list of vices (Col 3:8) is separated from one exhortation in particular, lying.¹⁰⁴ Paul urges his audience to put aside the vices (Col 3:8), which is part of divesting or taking off the old clothes (Col 3:9).

B. Community Life as Transformation into the Image of Christ (Colossians 3:9–14)

⁹Do not lie to one another, seeing that you have stripped off the old self with its practices ¹⁰and have clothed yourselves with the new self, which is being renewed in knowledge according to the image of its creator. ¹¹In that renewal there is no longer Greek and Jew, circumcised and uncircumcised, barbarian, Scythian, slave and free; but Christ is all and in all! ¹²As God’s chosen ones, holy and beloved, clothe yourselves with compassion, kindness, humility, meekness, and patience. ¹³Bear with one another and, if anyone has a complaint against another, forgive each other; just as the Lord has forgiven you, so you also must forgive. ¹⁴Above all, clothe yourselves with love, which binds everything together in perfect harmony. (Col 3:9–14; NRSV)

As in Eph 4:22–24, τὸν παλαιὸν ἄνθρωπον is translated to “old person” or “old self” by the NRSV, NIV, and ESV. By contrast the NET and KJV translate ἄνθρωπον as “man,” which at least gets at the collective sense of the word (even in its dated use). The CEB translates the same

¹⁰⁴ For more on lying, see Nijay K. Gupta’s commentary, *Colossians* (Macon, GA: Smyth & Helwys, 2013), specifically his interpretation sidebar, “Lying Problems in Colossae?,” 137.

phrase here as “old human nature” and “new nature” (Col 3:9–10; CEB). I will continue to use translate τὸν παλαιὸν ἄνθρωπον and τὸν νέον as “the old humanity” and “the new [humanity]” (Col 3:9–10).

Col 3:9–10 sets into motion a section of ethical commands and behaviors, modeled by Christ (Col 3:11b). “The new humanity is being renewed” (Col 3:10) just as the “inner person is being renewed day by day” (2 Cor 4:16). 2 Cor 4:16 and Col 3:10 are the only places in the New Testament where ἀνακαινῶω (being made new) is used. A similar word, ἀνακαινώσις (renewal), is used in Rom 12:2 and Titus 3:5. Both are attached to continual transformation and regeneration. So too, the renewal in Col 3:10 is a continual process, which transforms the new humanity into the renewed image of God (3:10b). While the words used for being renewed are different in Eph 4 and Col 3, they hold the same meaning.

As James G. Dunn put it, in holding “together creation and salvation”. . . Paul message “has the effect of reminding the readers that Christian ethics is not a matter merely of individual resolve, but involves a corporate dimension; Adam christology leads directly into a theology of the body of Christ.”¹⁰⁵ The old humanity that is to be stripped off is the old Adam and the practices of fallen humanity.¹⁰⁶ The practices are not intrinsic to humanity, but are, as Gupta puts it, the “effects of sin, the trappings of the old man.”¹⁰⁷ The community is being renewed (ἀνακαινούμενον); or as Gupta puts it, “reverting back to an originally intended perfect state,” if

¹⁰⁵ James D.G. Dunn, *The Epistles to the Colossians and to Philemon: A Commentary on the Greek Text* (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1996), 222.

¹⁰⁶ The creation language beckons back to 1 Cor 15:42–49.

¹⁰⁷ Gupta, *Colossians*, 140.

“perfect” is understood as “complete.”¹⁰⁸ God continues to recreate humanity into God’s own image, modeled by Christ, who is “all in all” (Col 3:11). The renewal brings together all kinds of people who are different from each other. The differences no longer define who they are in Christ. No longer is humanity defined by ethnicity, family, religious practice, or social status. The renewal brings unity between individuals and people groups, because Christ remains completely at the center of life (Col 3:11).

Paul continues, saying, “as God’s chosen ones, holy and beloved, clothe yourselves with compassion, kindness, humility, meekness, and patience” (Col 3:12; NRSV). The new set of clothes, rooted in the resurrection, is ethics to live by. The ethics of the resurrection is there for binding the community closer together (Col 3:13–14). The distinction people used to divide itself is no longer appropriate for the new humanity. Just as Paul called the Corinthians to bear the image and death of Jesus in their body (1 Cor 15:49; 2 Cor 4:11), he calls the Colossians, in turn, to bear with one another in forgiveness (Col 3:13). Col 3:12–14 sets more constructive community ethics for the church to practice. The community that practices these renewed behaviors reflects the image of the creator-God, in Christ.

C. Comparison of the Greek Text of Ephesians 4:22–25 to Colossians 3:9–14

The similarities between Eph 4:22–24 and Col 3:8–10 are striking.¹⁰⁹ First, both passages speak of taking off the old humanity along with the behaviors and practices associated with that old way of life (Eph 4:22; Col 3:9). Paul does not leave the community bare, but commands them to put on a new way of life, both according to the likeness or image of God (Eph 4:24b; Col 3:10b). Second, both speak about renewal (Eph 4:23; Col 3:10). A present renewal, initiated by

¹⁰⁸ Gupta, *Colossians*, 140.

¹⁰⁹ Please see the Appendix for a comparison of the two Greek texts.

God's Spirit, to a just and holy way of living (Eph 4:24) that reflects all of humanity, in Christ (Col 3:11). Finally, both have conjunctions. Paul, in Eph 4, says, therefore (διὸ) put away falsehood (Eph 4:25) and in Col he says, therefore (οὖν) "clothe yourselves with compassion, kindness, humility, meekness, and patience" (Col 3:12). These two sections from Eph 4–5 and Col 3 summarize the second way to describe the resurrection life, which is to take off unethical behaviors that do not bring about righteousness and holiness and put on ethical behaviors that create and maintain a flourishing community.

CONCLUSION: APPLICATION OF THE ETHICS OF THE RESURRECTION LIFE

The eschatological foundation in 1 Cor 15 and 2 Cor 4–5 sets up Eph 4 and Col 3 as texts of profound ethical practices to follow. Paul stressed the community life and tied it to the transformation because of the Christ-event. The message to take off the old humanity, along with its practices, and put on the practices associated with the new humanity, rooted in Christ, is a message that rings true today.

There is a great need for a focus on renewal and reconciliation in the church. Similarly, as in Ephesus and Colossae, the church needed grounding for their ethics. The reconciliation found in the new humanity of Christ (1 Cor 15 and 2 Cor 4–5) is to be lived out in community through practical ways of clothing itself with “equity and holiness” and “heartfelt compassion, kindness, humility, gentleness, patience. . . , and love” (Eph 4:24; Col 3:12, 14). The church needs to seek renewal and restoration within its own communities and model Christ's resurrection life for the world. If the church clothes itself with a resurrection ethic, rooted in the image of God, realized in Christ, and sustained by God's Spirit, reconciliation is possible.

These four passages together make the case that Paul's use of clothing and investiture, grounded in the hope of resurrection, generates an alternative praxis for Christian living in the image of the risen Christ. The Corinthian correspondence describe resurrection ethics as mortality putting on immortality, marked by a cruciform life for others. Eph and Col describe resurrection ethics as putting off unethical practices and putting on ethical practices that bring wholeness and peace into community life and the world.

This may seem like an overstatement, but I sense a lack of effort, enthusiasm, and true participation from many church-goers, today. When someone chooses to follow the example of

Jesus, there is a change, but more often than not, the new-believer's passion fades over time. Being a Christian simply turns into weekly attendance where the congregation is fed in some way and life returns to unfulfilling, mundane tasks. "But, that is not how you learned Christ" (Eph 4:20). Paul has made it clear that following the resurrection life includes many choices; choices that alter the flourishing of a community and the world.

How many of the communal ethical practices are missing from church life today? How much is integrated into a community's liturgy? Paul calls his audience to clothe themselves with "compassion, kindness, humility, meekness, and patience" and to "bear with one another and...forgive each other..."and" above all, clothe [them]selves with love, which binds everything together in perfect harmony" (Col 3:12-14; NRSV). Paul is urging the community to practice these things. This kind of practice is Christ-centered and will raise up communities in the image of the new humanity, which has died and been raised with the crucified and risen Lord. Community life will still have problems (why Paul wrote in the first place), but those who clothe themselves with the new humanity are equipped to address challenging problems and behave more like Christ. The ethics of the resurrection challenges the ordinary way of living and affects all of life. What sort of clothes will you choose to wear?

APPENDIX: COMPARISON OF EPHESIANS 4:22–25 AND COLOSSIANS 3:9–12

Ephesians 4:22–25 Greek Text

²²ἀποθέσθαι (AMN—to put away) ὑμᾶς κατὰ τὴν προτέραν ἀναστροφὴν (ASF—previous behavior) τὸν παλαιὸν ἄνθρωπον (ASM—the old humanity) τὸν φθειρόμενον κατὰ τὰς ἐπιθυμίας τῆς ἀπάτης, ²³ἀνανεοῦσθαι (PPN—to renovate/reform) δὲ τῷ πνεύματι τοῦ νοῦς ὑμῶν, ²⁴καὶ ἐνδύσασθαι (AMN—to clothe/put on) τὸν καινὸν ἄνθρωπον (ASM—the new humanity) τὸν κατὰ θεὸν κτισθέντα (ASMAPP—to create/find) ἐν δικαιοσύνῃ καὶ ὁσιότητι τῆς ἀληθείας. ²⁵Διὸ (therefore) ἀποθέμενοι τὸ ψεῦδος λαλεῖτε ἀλήθειαν ἕκαστος μετὰ τοῦ πλησίον αὐτοῦ, ὅτι ἐσμὲν ἀλλήλων μέλη.

Colossians 3:9–12 Greek Text

⁹μὴ ψεύδεσθε εἰς ἀλλήλους, ἀπεκδυσάμενοι (NPMAMP—to take off) τὸν παλαιὸν ἄνθρωπον (ASM—the old humanity) σὺν ταῖς πράξεσιν αὐτοῦ (DPF—along with its practices), ¹⁰καὶ ἐνδυσάμενοι (NPMAMP—to clothe/put on) τὸν νέον (ASM—the new) τὸν ἀνακαινούμενον (ASMPPP—to renovate) εἰς ἐπίγνωσιν κατ' εἰκόνα τοῦ κτίσαντος (GSMAAP—to create/find) αὐτόν, ¹¹ὅπου οὐκ ἔνι Ἕλληνα καὶ Ἰουδαῖον, περιτομὴ καὶ ἀκροβυστία, βάρβαρος, Σκύθης, δοῦλος, ἐλεύθερος, ἀλλὰ [τὰ] πάντα καὶ ἐν πᾶσιν Χριστός. ¹²Ἐνδύσασθε (2PAMM—clothe yourselves!) οὖν (therefore) ὡς ἐκλεκτοῦ τοῦ θεοῦ, ἅγιοι καὶ ἠγαπημένοι, σπλάγχνα οἰκτιρμοῦ, χρηστότητα, ταπεινοφροσύνην, πραύτητα, μακροθυμίαν.

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